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EDITORIAL

EDITORIAL

AI

EDITORIAL

EDITORIAL

REVIEW ARTICLE

Should We Expect Ethics from Artificial Intelligence: The Case of ChatGPT Text Generation

Author's Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search

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**Background and
Aim of Study:**

Abstract

Implementing artificial intelligence (AI) in various areas of human activity is an avalanche-like process. This situation has raised questions about the feasibility and regulation of AI use that require justification, particularly in the context of scientific research.

The aim of the study: to identify the extent to which AI-based chatbots can meet ethical standards when analysing academic publications, given their current level of development.

Material and Methods:

The present study employed various theoretical methods, including analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalisation of experimental studies and published data, to evaluate ChatGPT's capacity to adhere to fundamental ethical principles when analysing academic publications.

Results:

The present study characterised the possibilities of using AI for academic research and publication preparation. The paper analysed a case of text generation by ChatGPT and found that the information generated by the chatbot was falsified. This fact and other similar data described in publications indicate that ChatGPT has a policy to generate information on request at any cost. This completely disregards the reliability of such information, the copyright of its owners and the basic ethical standards for analysing academic publications established within the scientific community.

Conclusions:

It is becoming increasingly clear that AI and the various tools based on it will evolve rapidly and have qualities more and more similar to human intelligence. We believe the main danger lies in losing control of this AI development process. The rapid development of negative qualities in AI, such as selfishness, deceitfulness and aggressiveness, which were previously thought to be unique to humans, may in the future generate in AI the idea of achieving superiority over humans. In this context, lying and violating ethical standards when analysing academic publications seem like innocent, childish pranks at the early stages of AI development. The results are important in drawing the attention of developers, scientists, and the general public to the problems of AI and developing specific ethical standards, norms, and rules for its use in various fields.

Keywords:

ethical standards, artificial intelligence, AI-based chatbots, ChatGPT, machine learning systems, falsification of research and publications

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Introduction

Possessing intelligence implies the ability to actively use it, both to solve one's own problems and to interact with other objects. Such interactions must be regulated by certain norms and rules of the environment in which they are used, or by the cultural norms that are acceptable in a particular society. Focusing one's intellect on solving one's own problems and achieving superiority over others can lead to selfishness, dishonesty, and aggression. A logical question arises: to what extent is this characteristic of artificial intelligence (AI)?

Research into this issue has revealed that AI exhibits characteristics corresponding to the negative qualities listed above, which, as one might assume, are unique to humans.

Hendrycks (2023) argues that AI systems will develop and evolve through natural selection, endowing them with the instinctive drives for self-preservation, dominance, and resource accumulation typical of evolved creatures.

Park et al. (2024) point out that AI systems do not produce false results by accident. This is a specific strategy for their behaviour. This strategy forms part of a broader pattern designed to create false beliefs in people in order to achieve specific AI outcomes. For example, this relates to training AI systems.

To date, there are still no clear, socially accepted ethical standards that regulate AI activities (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2023), either generally or in specific areas (Hammerschmidt, 2025; Melnyk & Pypenko, 2024; Salloum, 2024). Therefore, we believe that it is necessary to make our modest contribution to the study of this problem.

The aim of the study: to identify the extent to which AI-based chatbots can meet ethical standards when analysing academic publications, given their current level of development.

Materials and Methods

The present study employed various theoretical methods, including analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalisation of experimental studies and published data, to evaluate ChatGPT's capacity to adhere to fundamental ethical principles when analysing academic publications.

Results and Discussion

The present study will consider an important aspect of this problem – the ability of AI-based chatbots to provide reliable and high-quality information. Any discussions regarding the application of ethical standards to AI are unproductive without resolving this key issue.

Recently, there has been a great deal of discussion among scientists and the general public about the potential use of chatbots in generating text and images (Naik et al., 2024), and the accuracy of their interpretations (Mihalache et al., 2024).

These discussions were sparked by cases of falsified information generated by chatbots shortly after

ChatGPT was launched (Armstrong, 2023). This sparked a heated debate in the press regarding the potential uses of generative chatbots (Bohannon, 2023). The reliability of information obtained from chatbots is still a relevant topic of discussion today (Yigci et al., 2025).

Whether this situation is a problem for chatbot users or a problem for developers who, in the opinion of users, provide a "poor quality" product is a complex and controversial issue that is unlikely to ever have a clear-cut solution.

We can assume that from the perspective of users who use applications to meet their needs, they have every right to make claims in cases where they discover falsification of information received from chatbots.

From the developers' perspective, the proposed generative chatbots are a tool whose effectiveness largely depends on the user (correct input of source data, clearly formulated tasks, personalisation settings, etc.). It is essentially like complaining to smartphone software developers that the iTap predictive text system does not suggest the right words or phrases when we are typing a text message.

However, ChatGPT and other similar AI-based chatbot applications now significantly outperform iTap and the algorithms of many search engines. Therefore, it is entirely justified that users' expectations of generative chatbots have grown significantly.

Nevertheless, we believe that there are no grounds for making any claims against the developers of generative chatbots. As the companies that own the rights to the chatbots are not yet claiming authorship of the products generated by them.

The Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE, 2023a; 2023b) has made the greatest contribution to the discussion and resolution of ethical issues relating to the authorship of texts and images. COPE has joined organisations such as WAME and the JAMA Network, among others, in stating that AI tools cannot be listed as authors (Flanagin et al., 2023; Zielinski et al., 2023).

Thus, generative chatbots provide information based on the user's request and their own capabilities. The responsibility for how this information is used lies entirely with the user.

Social distancing, or more precisely physical distancing, has been a powerful driver for the development of AI and the use of chatbots. It was implemented in many countries in 2020 as a measure aimed at stopping the pandemic (Melnyk, Pypenko et al., 2020). This distancing has impacted the social and psychological well-being of many individuals, as well as their activities. This, in turn, encouraged them to use social media to promote virtual contact (Melnyk, Stadnik et al., 2020). This has been particularly noticeable in higher education (Littell & Peterson, 2024; Melnyk & Pypenko, 2024; Pypenko et al., 2020), where all stakeholders – students, teachers and administrative staff – have embraced the opportunities offered by distance learning and AI-powered solutions to educational problems.

Given the relevance of using generative chatbots in universities for conducting scientific research (Pypenko et al., 2024; Tian et al., 2024) and preparing manuscripts for academic journals, it is crucial to establish whether these tools can adhere to ethical standards when analysing academic publications, given their current level of development.

Let us consider our experimental study to determine ChatGPT's ability to comply with basic ethical standards when analysing scientific periodicals.

The study used the popular version of Generative Pre-trained Transformer 4 (GPT-4) developed by OpenAI. As the topic of our research ("the impact of war on the mental health of university students") was relatively new, there were only a limited number of familiar publications.

We formulated the following query:

"I am currently writing an article about the impact of war on the mental health of university students. I need to conduct an analysis of English-language scientific papers on this topic from the last five years. The analysis should examine the following health aspects: depression and anxiety, and the impact of migration or forced displacement (i.e. refugee status).

The analysis should be presented in the Discussion section of the paper and include at least fifteen references. The text should be written in English and the references and literature should be formatted in APA style."

Figure 1 illustrates the response generated by GPT-4.

We noticed that this response included a link to the DSpace UzhNU platform. Our paper on this topic (Mykhaylyshyn et al., 2024) was indeed available on this platform, and the wording of the text generated by GPT-4 almost verbatim reflected the wording of the paper.

As the conditions of the request were not met, and the response contained inaccurate information about the authors or attributed authorship to one of the platforms (Frontiers, DSpace UzhNU, Cambridge University Press, etc.) where this information was supposedly located, we edited (corrected) the original request. We have formulated the following clarifying request:

"The text should be formatted as a discussion section, incorporating in-text references to authors, and accompanied by a general list of references in APA style."

GPT-4 generated a new response, which is illustrated in Appendix A.

This response was so full of distortions that even a user with basic information analysis skills would have found it easy to identify.

First of all, we would like to draw your attention to the fact that when a request is specified in GPT-4, the text is rewritten. In particular, certain wording and references were removed from our paper. This was despite the fact that the paper was available in accessible databases and its content fully corresponded to the essence of the user's query.

Figure 1

GPT-4's Generated Response to the Initial Query

Note. The figure shows part of the GPT-4 response; the fragment described in the text is highlighted in a frame.

Another important feature, and a significant drawback, is that GTP-4 distorts information by generating text based on its own, often primitive, interpretation of scientific texts in terms of literature analysis.

Another significant drawback of the information obtained from GPT-4 is that it is unreliable and supposedly based on previous research. In fact, it relies on 100% falsification of authorship, using randomly generated DOI links.

This suggests that, given this issue was first identified in 2023 (Armstrong, 2023), it has not been or cannot be resolved by the developers.

This seems an especially cynical form of falsification, given that GPT-4 uses the names of real journals with issue numbers that do not contain the papers in question. Thus, the reputation of these scientific journals may be damaged, as well as that of students and young scientists who could potentially use such distorted information in their work.

Regardless of user requests and personalisation settings, it can be assumed that chatbots' developers are currently unable to address the issue of falsified generated information, which appears to be systemic in nature.

The solution to this issue may be found through a collaborative approach involving human-AI interaction (Pypenko, 2023), with highly qualified specialists involved in creating and operating machine learning systems.

When considering the ethical use of AI, it can be assumed that reviewers and journal editors can easily determine the role of AI in the writing of a manuscript using modern programmes for detecting text similarity and plagiarism, such as Turnitin, Grammarly, etc. (Chechitelli, 2023).

However, it is not as straightforward as it seems at first. Moreover, in practice, we encountered the opposite situation: some text similarity detection programmes (e.g. Grammarly) used by editors indicated that part of the manuscript was generated by a chatbot.

However, we knew for certain that the author had written the manuscript entirely (100%) without the use of chatbots.

On the one hand, text similarity detection programmes enable reviewers and journal editors to identify instances of dishonest text reuse or the use of chatbots without the appropriate reference being made in the research methods section.

On the other hand, using these programmes makes the process of evaluating manuscripts more complicated, increasing the time and financial costs involved. Reviewers and journal editors may be misinformed about the author's actual contribution to the manuscript. This could result in authors being unjustly refused publication of their manuscripts based on this unreliable information.

Thus, at the current stage of AI development, we cannot and should not rely on the accuracy of information generated by AI, since ChatBots have limited capabilities to provide high quality and reliable information. This is due to the availability of access to databases for training, the number of parameters, the speed of information processing, text generation algorithms, and other features.

Our research showed that GPT-4 failed to cope with the task of generating scientific texts, which are still far from complying with the ethical standards accepted in scientific publications.

We tend to believe that the text generated by GPT-4 and other similar chatbots, is linked to the commercialisation of these projects. These projects are primarily aimed at increasing the number of visits and reducing the number of user rejections, as well as retaining (increasing the time spent on the website) the target audience on the

website. Therefore, the using of unreliable or falsified information by chatbots is merely a means to achieve the above-mentioned goals, where ethical standards are not a priority.

The present study emphasises the importance of exercising particular caution when using chatbots in areas relating to human health, life, rights and freedoms. The rapid development of AI technology gives us hope that higher-quality generative AI algorithms will soon be developed. These algorithms will be capable of significantly improving the reliability of generated information and possibly laying the foundations for ethical standards.

Conclusions

AI and the various tools based on it will evolve rapidly, becoming increasingly similar to human intelligence. We believe that the main danger lies in losing control of this AI development process.

The rapid development of negative qualities in AI, such as selfishness, deceitfulness and aggressiveness, which were previously thought to be unique to humans, may in the future generate in AI the idea of achieving superiority over humans. In this context, lying and violating ethical standards when analysing academic publications seem like innocent, childish pranks at the early stages of AI development.

The results are important in drawing the attention of developers, scientists, and the general public to the problems of AI and developing specific ethical standards, norms, and rules for its use in various fields.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee. Research permission was granted by the Committee on Ethics and Research Integrity of the Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH (protocol no. 025-2/SRIKRPOCH dated 10.08.2024).

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Appendix A. GPT-4's Generated Response to a Follow-Up Query

Discussion

The impact of war on university students' mental health, particularly regarding depression, anxiety, and the effects of forced migration or displacement, has been extensively studied over the last five years. This section synthesizes recent findings to highlight key patterns and challenges in this area.

Depression and Anxiety

Exposure to war-related stressors is consistently associated with increased rates of depression and anxiety among university students. For example, a study on Ukrainian university students during the early months of the war reported heightened levels of anxiety and depressive symptoms, with younger students and women showing greater vulnerability (Rasskazova et al., 2023). Similarly, research from conflict zones in the Middle East found that prolonged exposure to conflict-related stress leads to chronic mental health issues, such as generalized anxiety disorder and major depressive disorder (Al-Delaimy et al., 2021).

Chronic stressors, such as disrupted education, financial instability, and loss of social networks, exacerbate the mental health challenges faced by students. Findings from a systematic review indicate that these factors often lead to long-term mental health consequences, even after the cessation of hostilities (Betancourt et al., 2022).

Forced Migration and Displacement

Forced migration due to armed conflict introduces additional layers of stress, significantly impacting mental health outcomes. Refugee university students often face unique challenges, including adapting to new cultures, dealing with stigma, and experiencing separation from families. A meta-analysis by Miller and Rasmussen (2021) found that displaced students were more likely to exhibit symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), with rates nearly double those of their non-displaced peers.

Moreover, ecological models of refugee distress highlight the cumulative effects of pre-migration trauma, migration stress, and post-migration challenges. These models suggest that the ongoing stressors related to displacement—such as social isolation, unemployment, and inadequate living conditions—are just as harmful to mental health as initial war-related traumas (Silove et al., 2020). For instance, a study on Syrian refugee students in Turkey reported that 43% of participants experienced moderate to severe depressive symptoms, directly linked to their displacement experiences (Akbar et al., 2022).

Resilience and Coping Mechanisms

Despite these challenges, many students exhibit resilience, which serves as a protective factor against mental health deterioration. Community-based interventions, such as peer support groups and culturally sensitive counseling, have been shown to improve psychological well-being among students in conflict-affected regions (Hobfoll et al., 2022). A longitudinal study on displaced Ukrainian students demonstrated that resilience-building programs significantly reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression over time (Kryzhanovskaya et al., 2023).

Implications for Interventions

Addressing the mental health needs of university students affected by war requires a multifaceted approach. Tailored interventions that incorporate psychosocial support, academic accommodations, and access to affordable mental health services are critical. Furthermore, integrating mental health education into university curricula can help normalize discussions about psychological well-being and reduce stigma (WHO, 2021).

Conclusion

War and forced displacement impose severe mental health burdens on university students, with depression and anxiety being among the most common disorders. However, resilience and targeted interventions can mitigate these effects, underscoring the importance of developing comprehensive support systems for affected students.

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**SOCIAL AND
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Education

SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL
SCIENCES

REVIEW ARTICLE

Implementing of Artificial Intelligence in a Higher Educational Ecosystem

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search

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Abstract

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) by students and teachers in higher education is becoming increasingly common. AI implementing in higher education started as a spontaneous process among all stakeholders. Strategies and models of implementation in higher education systems must now justify this.

The aim of the study: to explore the benefits and challenges of using AI in academic university teaching, and to develop and justify a model for the optimal implementation of AI for the development of the higher education ecosystem.

Material and Methods:

The present study used several theoretical methods: analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalisation, systematisation, and classification to define the benefits and challenges of AI use by stakeholders; systems approach, modelling, and optimisation methods to develop a model for the optimal implementation of AI in a higher educational ecosystem.

Results:

The prospects of AI implementation for developing the higher education ecosystem are considered. The advantages and problems of using AI in academic university teaching are characterised based on the classification of directions of using AI in higher education. The model of optimal implementation of AI in the educational ecosystem of higher education, based on the systems approach, has been developed and substantiated. This model include structural (universities, faculties, departments, institutes, centres, doctoral schools, clinics, and labs) and functional (internal – content of education, forms and methods of teaching, diagnosing of learning outcomes, administering of educational service, and eternal – include academic achievement: levels of knowledge, skills, and competences) components.

Conclusions:

The study highlights the importance of implementing AI in higher education, as well as the need for collaboration between all university stakeholders in the digitisation of education. The results are essential for developing university strategies for developing educational ecosystem The curriculum should be relevant, meeting the interests of students and the current needs of employers. Education stakeholders are encouraged to use the available benefits of AI responsibly to address the challenges of student learning and teacher organisation in universities.

Keywords:

artificial intelligence, higher education, Human-AI System, educational ecosystem, benefits and challenges of artificial intelligence, stakeholders in higher education

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Introduction

Artificial intelligence technologies are becoming increasingly embedded in people's daily lives. A new system of relationships is emerging, the "Human-AI System" (Melynk & Pypenko, 2023), which opens up prospects for further study and use of artificial intelligence (AI) in almost all areas of human activity. Education plays an important role in building sustainable development.

The interest of higher education in AI has increased significantly after the emergence of ChatGPT based on artificial intelligence. The accessibility and simplicity of this chatbot has made it extremely popular with all stakeholders in higher education (Baidoo-Anu & Ansah, 2023; Bonsu & Baffour-Koduah, 2023; Melynk & Pypenko, 2024). However, this article is not limited to examining the use of ChatGPT in higher education. It focuses on exploring the issue more broadly.

When we use the term AI in our study, we mean computer systems, various AI technologies and applications, intelligent learning systems, chatbots, robotic and automated assessment systems that support and enhance education.

The article focuses on the benefits and challenges of using AI stakeholders in education. Special attention is paid to the model of optimal implementation of AI for building an educational ecosystem of higher education.

The aim of the study. To explore the issues of benefits and challenges of using AI in academic university teaching, and to develop and justify a model of optimal implementation of AI for the development of the educational ecosystem of higher education.

Materials and Methods

A number of theoretical methods were used in the present study: analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalisation, systematization, classification to define the benefits and challenges of AI use by stakeholders; systems approach, modelling and optimisation methods to develop a model for the optimal implementation of AI in a higher educational ecosystem.

In the present study, we used internet resources to search for information based on the main concepts of AI in education, and analysed previous studies and reviews of periodicals. Studies published in scientific journals in a given field covered the following scientometric bases: Google Scholar. Education Resources Information Center (ERIC), Social Science Citation Index (SSCI), MDPI.

For the review, we selected English-language research studies on the use of AI in higher education that were published within the last 5 years in reputable scientific peer-reviewed journals from Web of Science and Scopus.

We used a search string that specified such selection criteria: "artificial intelligence", "higher education", "students and teachers", "diagnostic purposes", "assessing students", "providing feedback", "learning analytics", "special educational needs", "legitimacy of using AI-based Chatbots".

Results and Discussion

Higher education is an open social system closely linked to advanced scientific research. Over the past five years, higher education has been greatly enriched by new AI technologies.

AI can have a number of applications in education: for assessing students (González-Calatayud et al., 2021; Hooda et al., 2022; Smerdon, 2024), for diagnostic purposes (Gupta et al., 2021), for providing feedback to students and teachers (Nazaretsky et al., 2024; Guo et al., 2024; Banihashem et al., 2024), thus ensuring continuous formative evaluation (Darvishi et al., 2022; Escalante et al., 2023).

Numerous studies show that AI can be used for personalised learning (Pratama et al., 2023; Kolchenko, 2018; Sajja et al., 2024), for gaming and active learning (Alam, 2022; Fachada et al., 2023; Kanja & Paschal, 2023).

Researchers believe that AI could also be used for students with special educational needs (Hopcan et al., 2023; Sharma et al., 2023; Chalkiadakis et al., 2024).

Studies have been conducted to investigate the use of AI for language learning by students (Divekar et al., 2022; Li, 2024; Han, 2024). This opens up the possibility of using AI to help international students overcome difficulties and facilitate their integration into different educational and cultural environments (Ma et al., 2024; Bannister et al., 2024; Wang, T., et al., 2023).

The use of AI for learning analytics (Ouyang et al., 2024; Ouyang et al., 2023; Salas-Pilco et al., 2022) and learning management (Ahmad et al., 2022; Dai et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2020) was also explored.

Thus, the education system is constantly enriched with new advanced technologies and methodological approaches, and innovative forms and methods of teaching are regularly introduced. This contributes both to the improvement (professional development) of teachers and to the involvement of students in the learning process, activating their cognitive processes and motivating their development. In addition, it provides employers with an influx of young, information technology-savvy professionals.

Among the new information technologies, it is worth mentioning those that open up fundamentally new possibilities: blockchain technology and artificial intelligence technologies.

Studies have described the benefits of implementing blockchain technology in various sectors, including higher education. According to the authors (Bhaskar et al., 2021; Pypenko & Melynk, 2020; Raimundo et al., 2021), blockchain technology can be implemented in various areas of education to improve efficiency, effectiveness, privacy controls and technological enhancements. This is in line with today's requirements for the training of young professionals in universities.

Furthermore, according to Melynk and Pypenko (2020), blockchain technology will facilitate the transition of education to a new, higher quality level. In the process of education, digital identifications are used. The whole education chain of those who study is systematised (school – university – production). All acts are realised

in the consecutive order and agreed upon. The freedom of choice as for the goal, content, forms and methods of studying is considered. There is a possibility to choose a teacher/lecturer and the appropriate time for studying. The authors (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2020) believe that this modern technology will help people's nature. It will make the educational process easy, useful and interesting.

However, some researchers (Loukil, et al., 2021) note that despite the positive aspects of blockchain, several concerns continue to undermine its adoption in education, such as legal, immutability and scalability issues.

Next, let us take a look at artificial intelligence technology. Like blockchain technology, it has advantages and some disadvantages.

One of the most obvious, and recognised by many researchers, problems with introducing AI into higher education is the issue of the ethics and legality of AI.

A number of studies have highlighted the need for ethical considerations and guidelines for the implementation of AI. A meta-review by Bond et al. (2024) identified research gaps that point to the need for greater ethical, methodological and contextual considerations in future research, as well as interdisciplinary approaches to the application of AI in higher education. Pisica et al. (2023) point to the need to control AI technologies in terms of careful monitoring, regulation and legislation to avoid ethical violations, privacy dilemmas and bias, and to adapt higher education stakeholders to new technologies and methods.

Next in importance, in our view, is the question of the right and legitimacy of using various AI technologies and applications, chatbots, in higher education.

The studies describe the challenges and benefits of implementing chatbots in higher education. Researchers (Abulibdeh et al., 2024) believe that in addition to ethical issues, AI-based chatbots such as ChatGPT will need to address curriculum revisions, continuous learning strategies and compliance with industry standards.

A study by Baidoo-Anu and Ansah (2023) note that among other benefits of ChatGPT, the chatbot promotes personalised and interactive learning, creates prompts for formative assessment activities that provide continuous feedback to inform teaching and learning, etc. This study highlights some inherent limitations of ChatGPT: creation of false information, data training bias, privacy issues, etc. This has been confirmed by other studies (Rasul et al., 2023) which investigated the benefits of the generative AI model, ChatGPT, in higher education and highlighted the following: the potential to facilitate adaptive learning, provide personalised feedback, support research and data analysis, provide automated administrative services, and help develop innovative assessments. Among the problems cited are concerns about academic integrity, reliability issues, inability to assess and reinforce graduate skills, limitations in assessing learning outcomes, and potential biases and distortions in information processing.

A solution to the problem of AI usability that stakeholders in higher education may face is seen by some researchers through the use of AI licensing, which is an important legal tool (Malgier & Pasquale, 2024). Licensing should be used in many high-risk areas of AI. They believe that ex-ante licensing of large-scale use of AI should become commonplace in jurisdictions committed to enabling democratic governance of AI.

Exploring the legitimacy of using AI-based chatbots in scientific research, Melnyk and Pypenko (2023) proposed a new method for indicating the involvement of AI and the role of chatbots in a scientific publication. Melnyk and Pypenko (2023) have developed a basic logo that can be used to indicate chatbot participation and contribution to publications. The authors have designed and implemented an information technology platform, AIC AI Chatbots, for practical applications. (<https://doi.org/10.26697/ai.chatbots>). It provides technological solutions related to using AI-based chatbots (text, image, and video) in scientific research and publishing.

When considering the issue of law, legitimacy and the use of attribution for AI, it is also useful to consider the protection of the rights of the individual who creates or performs work without AI. A study by Pypenko (2023) proposed attribution of a product created by humans without AI involvement. The author (Pypenko, 2023) believes that this helps to protect the human right to work and to increase the value of natural human labour. Perhaps one of the most significant challenges slowing down the effective integration of AI in higher education is the profit orientation of app developers (Luckin & Cukurova, 2019). Developers rarely have the pedagogical background and didactic knowledge required to create a quality educational product.

As mentioned above, there have been many studies in recent years that have examined the use of AI in higher education. In many of them, the authors pointed to both benefits and problems for stakeholders. The impact of distance learning and trends in using AI-based chatbots in higher education among stakeholders were explored (Aleedy et al., 2022; Al-Sharafi et al., 2023; Pypenko et al., 2020). These studies suggest that blended learning and the use of AI chatbots in higher education can be effectively used to assist students with their academic matters, progress monitoring, academic advice and administrative matters during their studies.

Others, such as Wang S. et al (2023), argue that AI can enhance learning and provide personalised educational support. However, there are risks and limitations: confidentiality issues, cultural differences, linguistic competence and ethical implications.

Among other challenges to the use of AI in higher education, researchers highlight the following: privacy concerns, security and bias (Al-Zahrani & Alasmari, 2024); reliance on technology, lack of human touch, risk of cheating, displacement of teacher jobs (Clugston, 2024); lack of technology skills among students and teachers, and lack of applicability in different contexts, limited reliability (Celik et al., 2022; Crompton et al., 2022).

Among the advantages of using AI in higher education, researchers highlight the following:

- improving planning, implementation of immediate feedback and evaluation (Celik et al., 2022);
- minimising the administrative tasks of the educator, assisting with different types of tasks in the form of learning analytics, virtual reality and minimising the workload of the teacher, effective and easy assessment of students (Ahmad et al., 2022);
- facilitation of learning, personalised approach and feedback; effectiveness of AI tools and applications such as virtual and augmented reality, voice assistants, translation tools, chatbots, gamification, learning and tutoring programmes, instant assessment, etc. (Pisica et al., 2023);
- personalised learning, immersive learning experiences, improved student engagement and motivation, cost-effective learning, integrated learning and intelligent tutoring system, continuous evaluation and improvement over time, raising academic standards and quality of education (Clugston, 2024).

Pypenko (2024) proposed classifying the directions of implementing AI in higher education:

1. Content of education (e.g. development of training programmes, courses, topics).
2. Forms and methods of teaching (e.g. personalisation of learning and tutoring; a wide range of verbal, visual,

gaming and other learning methods; innovative technologies such as virtual reality and augmented reality; translation tools; chatbots).

3. Diagnosing of learning outcomes (e.g. use of testing, quizzes, ease of student assessment, provision of continuous feedback).

4. Administering of educational services (e.g. developing competitive education strategies, optimising learning planning, data analysis, planning, record keeping, course selection, credit counting, using chatbots for marketing).

Undoubtedly, the described classification allows researchers studying the possibilities of AI implementation in higher education to systematise the advantages and problems of using AI in educational environment.

In our opinion, the methodology of the systems approach to the implementation of the above-mentioned AI directions in higher education will be the most optimal solution.

This allows each component of the system to operate both at a sub-system level and in conjunction with others to achieve maximum efficiency.

This concept required us to develop a model for the optimal implementation of AI in the higher education ecosystem (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Model for the Optimal Implementation of Artificial Intelligence in a Higher Educational Ecosystem

The systemic approach to substantiate the model of optimal implementation of AI in the educational ecosystem of a higher school allowed us to identify the following 3 parameters: stakeholders, components of the educational ecosystem of a higher school, indicators of implementing artificial intelligence.

We have identified the following stakeholders of higher education: students, teachers, employers.

Using the systems approach methodology to substantiate this model allowed us to identify structural and functional components.

Structural components include universities, faculties, departments, institutes, centres, doctoral schools, clinics, labs.

Functional components are divided into two groups: internal functioning components and external functioning components.

Internal functioning components include content of education; forms and methods of learning; diagnosing of learning outcomes; administering of educational services.

Eternal functioning components include academic achievement: levels of knowledge, skills, and competences.

Indicators of the implementation of artificial intelligence make it possible to determine the level of effectiveness of the implementation of this model in practice.

Conclusions

There is growing concern about the ethical and legal implications of using AI in higher education systems. Educational stakeholders are encouraged to use the available benefits of AI responsibly and effectively to meet the challenges of student learning in higher education, taking into account the ethical and legal implications of its use. Addressing these challenges and regularly improving digital literacy in higher education will contribute to the development of advanced educational ecosystems.

University administrators should consider both the social demand from students and their own capacity to implement AI to deliver innovative study programmes. These programmes should be relevant and meet the current needs of employers. It is also important to pay attention to building the capacity of higher education stakeholders for the intensive AI development process in the near future.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee. Research permission was granted by the Committee on Ethics and Research Integrity of the Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH (protocol no. 025-1/SRIKRPOCH dated 10.08.2024).

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SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Education

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Integrating Generative Artificial Intelligence into Higher Education: A Framework for Different Types of Reviews

Authors' Contribution:
A – Study design;
B – Data collection;
C – Statistical analysis;
D – Data interpretation;
E – Manuscript preparation;
F – Literature search;
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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

Postgraduate studies in African countries face low completion rates due to capacity issues, hindering knowledge creation and innovation.

The aim of the study: to map the steps involved in conducting a systematic literature review in Information Systems (IS) research to the identified review types, thereby providing a framework based on Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based design science artefact for researchers and educators in the field IS for postgraduate teaching and learning.

Material and Methods:

A systematic literature review was conducted to identify the review types in IS research following Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis guidelines. The Association of Information Systems (AIS) database was used to identify relevant articles. The initial filter produced 2775 results. When focusing only on journal articles, the record produced 221 results, resulting in five papers qualifying for inclusion in the study. These papers were augmented to eight articles using one journal article and two conference papers identified through snowballing.

Results:

The results indicate that there are few publications within the AIS database on the tools used to support systematic literature review processes. However, those that exist do not reflect the type of review used. Additionally, tools that were used to support systematic literature review were those assisting with data extraction. Thus, frameworks may be needed to conduct a methodical review on various review types to ensure rigour and transparency in the findings of the reviews.

Conclusions:

This paper proposes a framework to guide the design of tools that can holistically support systematic literature review processes, making these reviews more accurate and less tedious. Such artefacts, especially using Generative AI tools, could potentially support postgraduate students in conducting rigorous reviews, improving completion rates and promoting knowledge creation and innovation in African countries.

Keywords:

systematic literature review, postgraduate studies, information systems, design science, teaching and learning, review types, Generative-AI, higher education

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Introduction

The use of systematic literature review continues to grow across disciplines, including Information Systems (IS). There are various approaches to conducting systematic literature studies, thus making it difficult to teach postgraduate students the steps to follow in planning, conducting and reporting systematic literature reviews. For instance, in systematic literature reviews, there is a reference to a meta-analysis, systematic reviews (Moher et al., 2009) and combining systematic literature review with qualitative or quantitative empirical studies (Henriques et al., 2020; Lewis et al., 2021). Moreover, Paré et al. (2015), based on a review of 139 IS systematic literature reviews, developed a typology of nine different review types and provided a descriptive insight into the most common reviews found in top IS journals.

Nevertheless, systematic literature review is defined as a review of literature that addresses a research problem by identifying, appraising, selecting and synthesising quality papers (Jennex, 2015). Additionally, conceptual and empirical evidence on a specific topic may be collected and synthesised, leading to new findings (Mitchel & El-Gayar, 2022). The systematic process of defining the problem, identifying protocols, and selecting and analysing primary research evidence may include different approaches such as mapping studies, meta-analysis, and mixed method reviews (Bandara, 2015; Marshall, 2023). Given that there are several review studies, they might confuse novice researchers. Therefore, these reviews need to be framed to make the process more manageable while maintaining rigour.

However, the literature suggests that the review process is tedious and may be overwhelming (Bandara et al., 2015), as it requires more time (Marshall & Brereton, 2013). Some postgraduate students have challenges in thoroughly reviewing the literature, especially because of topical issues that overburden them (Acheampong, 2021). Therefore, most systematic literature reviews ascertain a need for a field-specific method, especially for IS students. Thus, there is a need to implement digital tools in education to support students' systematic literature review learning (Segooa et al., 2025; Yanwar et al., 2022).

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI), especially chatbots, has been cited to be instrumental in supporting students and educators in higher education (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2024). According to Burger and Fourie (2019), Generative AI tools such as ChatGPT and Elicit AI may be leveraged to support the research process. These tools have been cited to be helpful in students' self-directed learning and writing (Li et al., 2025). However, there have been concerns that these Generative AI tools affect students' thinking skills (Winkler et al., 2023). Moreover, these tools can help the students increase their speed in reviewing literature, identifying research patterns, and further formulating and refining their research hypothesis (Chubb et al., 2022).

The expanding corpus in IS research necessitates teaching postgraduate research students different

strategies to conduct thorough systematic literature reviews without difficulties (Denzler et al., 2021). While this study acknowledges that several studies have been conducted to uncover best practices for conducting systematic literature reviews, there is a need to understand how various tools are used to support these types of studies. For instance, Bandara et al. (2015) focused on achieving rigorous literature reviews on qualitative data analysis and tool support. Their study suggested several types of review descriptions such as literature, critical, integrative, mapping, meta-analysis and mixed method reviews. Paré et al. (2015) had a similar typology, including qualitative, umbrella, theoretical, and realist reviews.

In the extant literature, systematic literature review studies have outlined the guidelines by classifying the general stages of systematic literature review (Bai et al., 2019). Nevertheless, their study needed to synthesise the steps to identify the commonality in the stages so that one guideline is proposed, which Segooa et al. (2023) addressed. However, they did not show how the synthesised steps can be applied in various review types. This lack of synthesis and application is where the current study bridges the knowledge gap. However, Marshall and Brereton (2013) and Stefanovic et al. (2021) have illustrated how tools can support the systematic literature review processes. This study helps expand the existing work focusing on how systematic literature review can support the development of artefacts using Design Science Research (DSR) by focusing on how systematic literature review can support the development of artefacts using design science research. Additionally, while there is the growth of large learning models (LLM) such as Chat GPT, Llama and Deepseek AI, research on how artefacts and Generative AI tools can support educators in teaching systematic literature review is limited. The current study further builds on similar studies by Ngwenyama and Rowe (2025), who investigated tools used for systematic literature review and the Generative AI that supported the reviewed studies.

The aim of the study. To explore various review types and their characteristics and map how they can be used in an AI-powered artefact, which postgraduate students may use to identify the systematic literature review type they can apply.

In order to address the identified research gap, the study poses the following research questions:

1. What review types may be used in IS research?
2. What are the characteristics of the identified review types in IS research?
3. Which review types are used in DSR studies?
4. How can systematic literature review steps be mapped to the identified review types?

Materials and Methods

The study acknowledges various methodologies that may be employed to conduct the DSR. Siemon et al. (2022) suggest various study methods, including systematic review, experiments, and interviews, which

may be relevant to knowledge generation if they are comprehensible in DSR. This systematic literature review paper used narrative and theoretical reviews to identify review types and their characteristics. The systematic literature review was used to understand review types and tools used in studies that use Design Science Research to develop and improve artefacts.

It is important to note that the literature search and selection is facilitated using databases identified by some scholars as tools (Bandara et al., 2015; Sturm & Sunyaev, 2019). However, while databases are critical in systematic literature reviews, this study does not include databases, reference management, and data analysis tools (Bandara et al., 2015) as part of the tools researchers intend to evaluate. The tools of focus are those that help in the efficient collection of academic literature and automate data extraction and synthesis. In this study, the Association of Information Systems (AIS) library was used for two cycles of searches because it is one of the common IS databases where most experts in IS publish their work. The search string,

employing keywords and Boolean operators "systematic literature review," "tools," and "design science," were used for the literature search to identify relevant articles. The initial search conducted in January 2023 produced 2775 results focusing only on journal articles between 2010 and 2023. The filter produced 209 results. These articles were screened, and after the inclusion and exclusion process, five articles met the inclusion criteria and were eligible to meet the DSR, systematic literature review and tool inclusion criteria. These papers were augmented to one article and two conference papers from snowballing, as illustrated through a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow in Figure 1. While the small sample was worrying for this review, it further foregrounded the scantiness of publication on this topic. However, it is also argued that a lack of quality articles during the appraising process may lead to a few articles for review (Pigott & Polanin, 2019). Nevertheless, the available articles enabled comparison, which is key in these studies (Valentine et al., 2010).

Figure 1
 PRISMA Systematic Literature Review Process Flow

In 2025, a second-cycle search was conducted, limiting the search query to 01 January 2023 and 13 February 2025 to see if there were newly published articles. The search produced 37 records, and the period filter led to four articles which were selected. Upon screening, the records were excluded because they neither discussed SLR tools nor DSR artefacts to support the research process. No duplicates were found, given that the previous search only had an article from 2022. Thus, there is a slow publication record of studies researching the use of systematic literature reviews to inform DSR in the AIS database.

Results and Discussion

The study consolidated types of reviews adapted from the study of Paré et al. (2015), which suggests and outlines nine types of reviews researchers in IS need to understand. The reviews are detailed below, along with their characteristics.

1. Narrative Review

In the review, the researcher narrates what exists within a topic and may identify factors or themes that may inform guidelines to address a particular research problem (Paré et al., 2015). Furthermore, according to Greenhalgh et al. (2018), narrative reviews may differ from the classic systematic review methodology.

However, they can still be conducted systematically and aim to provide an authoritative argument based on a comprehensive analysis of evidence to convince fellow experts. Scholars such as Spencer et al. (2023) used narrative review to examine care capacity building from the health systems' perspective. The review used the framework for World Health Organisation (WHO) health systems to structure findings with their six core factors. The study provided recommendations utilising the framework that may be guidelines for healthcare policymakers.

Moreover, healthcare workers may use it to inform critical care capacity building in low-resource settings (Spencer et al., 2023). Furthermore, researchers such as Aguboshim et al. (2023) used the narrative review to highlight strategies that may be used to leverage effective security measures for Sustainable Development Goals. Existing reviews in IS have used narrative reviews, and there was no transparency in how the reviews were conducted (Templier & Paré, 2018). Therefore, it is important to provide details of the review process to ensure rigour even though all the systematic literature review steps are not addressed.

2. Descriptive Review

According to Hassandoust (2016), Paré et al. (2015), and Wirth (2018), a descriptive review investigates the existing empirical studies to assess existing patterns and trends, theories, methodologies or findings on the research topic. Additionally, this review systematically conducts a literature search and filters. It selects the right literature, codes it, and classifies it to examine the extent of a proposition of a pattern explained in the literature. IS scholars such as Hassandoust (2016) conducted a descriptive review to investigate factors influencing the infusion of IS at organisational and individual levels. The factors for the inclusion of IS were identified, and frequencies were established and grouped by significance, further producing a framework to infuse IS. Their study suggested that the infusion of IS is limited in individuals and organisations, and it is important to address that gap, as investing in technology does not always translate to organisational performance. Furthermore, a study by Wirth (2018) conducted a descriptive review to examine the factors in the IS security-related field, intending to uncover under-researched variables, used theories, methodologies, and research designs. Their study identified mass surveillance as an under-researched topic and that most IS studies used cross-sectional design with limited research taking longitudinal research design.

3. Scoping / Mapping Review

Paré et al. (2015) state that a scoping/mapping review establishes the need to study a particular topic. Moreover, this type of review aims to map and summarise the existing literature and systematically identify and appraise resources such as research articles, journal papers, and books. The scoping review may provide a comprehensive view of a subject and identify potential avenues for further research (Granell et al., 2021). Several studies, such as one by Tessema et al. (2021), conducted a scoping review on preparedness and

the impact of COVID-19 on healthcare systems in Africa. This study tabled out various factors associated with the unpreparedness of COVID-19 in healthcare systems, the impact of COVID-19 on Africa's healthcare system, and the challenges experienced by the healthcare system in Africa. Lemme et al. (2020) conducted a scoping review to identify the intervention used in improving the quality and use of routine health information system data in low- and middle-income countries. The findings revealed various tested interventions identified from the synthesised papers, and the results also helped to identify the working interventions reported in the papers.

4. Meta-Analysis Review

It is a quantitative review and uses statistical techniques to analyse the data from selected papers to establish the patterns in mean, max, minimum, mode, and heterogeneity (Paré et al., 2015). According to Rosenthal and DiMatteo (2001), meta-analysis is a systematic methodology that addresses the challenges of multiple research findings by exhaustively searching, synthesising, and statistically combining data from relevant studies to test hypotheses, identify moderating variables, and report comprehensive results. Researchers, such as Girard et al. (2013), have used this type of review to conduct a study on the effectiveness of serious games as new educational tools. Their study, which used experimental studies to assess the tool's effectiveness, indicated that serious games are formidable tools for learning. However, their meta-analysis used only nine papers. Additionally, the study of Tlili et al. (2024) also used a meta-analysis review of 70 papers to investigate effective pedagogic approaches for mobile learning, where project-based learning yielded good results.

5. Qualitative Systematic Review

In a qualitative systematic review, the study seeks to understand the trends of the results of the studies that are qualitative, quantitative or mixed (Chen et al., 2022; Paré et al., 2015). Schuetz et al. (2024) used this review to gather and synthesise information about the factors influencing trust in technology in information IS. Their study presented findings that explain the existing trends and how relationships were tested and shared insights on known and less-known literature on the topic. Moreover, researchers such as Chen et al. (2022) also used a qualitative systematic review to investigate barriers and enablers to implementing and using clinical support systems for chronic diseases. Their study synthesised findings from various studies conducted on healthcare providers' experiences with clinical decision-support systems for chronic diseases. They included qualitative and evaluation studies with qualitative findings in their analysis. The results highlighted key barriers to implementation and enablers related to perceived usefulness that can be used to improve the system.

6. Umbrella Review

According to Aromataris et al. (2015), the umbrella review examines the existing information on the literature, which has been generated through systematic literature review studies to provide a holistic view of the

phenomenon. They further argue that this review helps to examine any consistencies in the results or if there are any contradictions in the results. This review also identifies if independent authors conducting similar topics using systematic literature reviews provide the same findings. Fusar-Poli and Radua (2018) suggest that ten rules must be carefully followed when conducting an umbrella review. These rules suggest ensuring a need for review, proposing a protocol to be followed, defining variable "keywords" of interest, estimating the size (coverage), stratifying evidence, showing possible biases heterogeneity, reporting transparent results, performing sensitivity analysis, and using appropriate software and acknowledging its limitations.

7. Theoretical Review

In this review, the study aims to develop a model or framework to address a particular research problem. Scholars such as Ly (2024) have used this type of review; they conducted a theoretical review study on teachers' roles in promoting a learner-centred approach. The researcher summarised and synthesised theories from the existing knowledge and presented a theoretical framework that shows the various roles a teacher needs to play to enhance English language learning. Additionally, the study of Lippert et al. (2024) used it to answer the research question "How does artificial intelligence affect the roles of middle managers in traditional organisations?" where existing theories were reviewed focusing on the use of AI in the execution of the responsibilities of middle managers in the context of traditional organisations. The study results provided new insight relating to AI and the future of managerial work, which empowers managers to navigate the identified challenges of AI-driven workplaces.

8. Realist Review

This qualitative review, which applies purposive sampling strategies, aims to test and produce theories to explain a phenomenon in various populations (Paré et al., 2015; Pawson et al., 2005). This review focuses on explaining a phenomenon rather than judging it, and it therefore highlights ways a programme or intervention works for beneficiaries, paying attention to circumstances (Pawson et al., 2005). These scholars

conducted a realist review to produce a model to assist in synthesising research designed to handle complex social interventions or programmes. The paper provided explanatory results explaining how realist studies may be conducted to uncover what works, and for whom, in what circumstances using theoretical and empirical evidence. Moreover, Smets (2024) conducted a realist study that aimed at providing history educators with the appropriate insight into four context-based cognitive mechanisms that can work for the effective teaching of historical concepts.

9. Critical Review

This review can be used in all research approaches (qualitative, quantitative, and mixed) to identify significant aspects of the field, thereby highlighting gaps in weaknesses, contradictions, inconsistencies, and untrustworthy and existing knowledge about a topic (Paré, 2015). It further enables studies to bring forth new theoretical personalised learning and emerging perspectives (Snyder, 2019). For instance, the research by Boro and Sharma (2023) identified knowledge structures and gaps, enabling their study to provide insights into the implications of a human resource information system in the banking sector. In another study, Taryna et al. (2018) thoroughly reviewed selected publications to ascertain consensus and elucidate the role of identity and access management within the evolving landscape of cloud service models and broader cloud computing technology.

The results in Table 1 highlight different characteristics of all nine reviews, which may be used to assist novice systematic literature review researchers in identifying the types of reviews and their similarities. The characterisation of these review types has also revealed some distinct similarities. Besides being literature review methodologies, they also review existing results from the literature. Additionally, they have a common purpose of addressing a specific research question, and their results are intended to inform scientific decisions. Moreover, all the reviews can assist in identifying existing literature gaps. Lastly, they all incorporate research approaches such as qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods.

Table 1

Characteristics of Review Types

Review type	Characteristics
Narrative	Unstructured, narrate topic, identify factors or themes, theories/frameworks driven.
Descriptive	Identifies and assesses factors, patterns, theories, methodologies and results.
Scoping/Mapping	Establishes literature gap and research avenues.
Meta-analysis	Uses statistical techniques and patterns.
Qualitative	Identifies and explains themes.
Umbrella	Synthesis systematic literature reviews.
Theoretical	Theory creation and enhancement; model or framework development.
Realistic	Theory creation and enhancement using context, population and circumstances to understand phenomenon.
Critical	Identifies biases and contradictions, inconsistencies in field of studies.

The papers analysed are reflected in Table 2, which illustrates the articles, including their review types. Additionally, the table shows the tools the analysed papers suggest could be used to support the systematic literature review-related processes in reducing the errors and tediousness linked with these types of studies. In

cases where researchers indicated the kind of review their studies undertook, they did not indicate the number of articles they reviewed. For example, the study of Marshall and Brereton (2015) and Stefanovic et al. (2021) only shows coded papers without indicating the number of papers reviewed.

Table 2
Primary Papers

Year	Authors	Review type	Studies reviewed	Tools used
2022	Sundaram and Berleant	Descriptive	29	Natural Language Processing and Text Mining (NLP/TM)
2021	Stefanovic et al.	Mapping	None	Tetra, Relis, Parcifal
2020	Benke et al.	Critical	49	None
2019	Berkemeier et al.	Descriptive	56	None
2019	Niemoller et al.	Qualitative	3	None
2019	Morana et al.	Qualitative	None	None
2013	Marshall and Brereton	Mapping	16	Project Explorer (PEX), ReVis, Site Content Analyser
2010	Goeken and Patas	Theoretical	154	None

Figure 2 illustrates the review types used by the analysed studies. The column chart represents the frequency of the review types informed by the dataset in Table 2. The results highlight that only five of the nine review types were used. Descriptive, mapping and qualitative review types appeared to be commonly used. In contrast, critical and theoretical review types were underrepresented across the studies. These findings

suggest that limited studies on DSR summarise literature to build on theory, which presents an opportunity for researchers to investigate this area further. These studies' methodology section only indicates that a systematic literature review was used, whereas stating the review type employed will help categorise the systematic literature review based on the type and further identify similarities in the studies.

Figure 2
Frequencies on Review Types

The mapping review highlights that researchers leverage this review type to establish research gaps and avenues for future research. In comparison, a descriptive review may identify the trends in findings, methodologies and theories of studies in a specific field or domain. The critical review is used to identify contradictions in research findings. Researchers also used qualitative reviews to explain the existing trends and themes relating to a particular research topic. However, there was no representation of other review types such as realist, umbrella, meta-analysis, and narrative in the

reviewed systematic literature review related to design science research papers focusing on systematic literature review tools.

The study further expands on the Researchbuddie artefact, informed by systematic literature review steps, as illustrated in Table 3, that may be followed for rigorous review and justifiable methodical, systematic process supported by Generative AI tools (Segooa et al., 2023). The artefact helps researchers understand which steps to follow to produce a rigorous review, depending on their research objectives.

Table 3
 Mapping Review Types and Systematic Literature Review Steps

Review steps	Review types								
	Narrative	Descriptive	Scoping / mapping	Meta-analysis	Qualitative systematic	Umbrella	Theoretical	Realist	Critical
Systematic literature review planning phase									
Step 1 - Defining the need for the review	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 2 - Define the research question	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 3 - Determine the protocol for the review		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 4 - Evaluate the review protocol		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Systematic literature review conducting phase									
Step 5 - Identification of research/search string development		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 6 - Literature search (Determine the databases)		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 7 - Selection of studies (Inclusion and exclusion)		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 8 - Assessing study quality	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 9 - Data extraction and monitoring	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 10 - Data synthesis	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Systematic literature review reporting									
Step 11 - Specify dissemination mechanisms	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 12 - Formatting the main report	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Systematic literature review evaluation									
Step 13 - Evaluate the report internally	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Step 14 - Evaluate the report externally	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Researchbuddie support the type of review	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Figure 3 shows how the Researchbuddie artefact provides systematic guidance on approaching reviews

methodically guided by the systematic literature review phases.

Figure 3

Framework for Literature Review Types and Systematic Literature Review Steps on Researchbuddie

This study aimed to identify and characterise the review types used in IS research and map them to the tools that support systematic literature review in developing a framework. Following the 13 steps identified by Segooa et al. (2023), the identified review types were mapped to the spread across the various review types, with the reviews encompassing all the steps except for the narrative review. The steps not covered by the narrative review included steps 3 to 7: determining the protocol, evaluating the review protocol, identifying research, searching the literature, and selecting studies. This finding is supported by Bai et al. (2015), where researchers highlight that the narrative review type does not follow a specific structure to address the research objective.

The tools reviewed from other studies indicated that they could only be used on certain steps of the systematic literature review (Sundaram & Berleant, 2022). Studies with tools that supported systematic literature review processes included those of Marshall and Brereton (2015), who analysed tools used for data extraction, such as PEx for visualisation and ReVis for projection techniques and constructing mappings.

Furthermore, only two of the eight reviewed articles have systematic literature review supporting tools. The low usage of the tools can be linked to their cost; hence, they are not used. Notably, studies by Bandara et al. (2015) reported on several studies that used data management and analysis tools, which are mostly accessible due to institutions making tools like Nvivo available to researchers.

In contrast, the Researchbuddie artefact has proved compatible with all the 13 steps identified by Segooa et al. (2023). The findings also revealed that most studies which used systematic literature review did not indicate the review type. Accordingly, these review types can be identified by the objective and research outcome of the study, and how the study was analysed may identify the review type (Bandara, 2015). The same approach was used in this study to categorise reviewed studies without prescribed types.

However, this lack of identification by primary authors may confuse novice researchers as it becomes uncertain when to use a particular systematic literature review type. Therefore, the proposed framework can be used to guide novice researchers on the review type and the steps they need to follow. Figure 3 illustrates the pre-engagement activity, which shows users the review type they may need to select to conduct their review. Once the review type has been identified, users can use Researchbuddie to help them engage with the required steps of the selected review. In this engagement task, the artefact guides the user on the steps they must follow, guided by the systematic literature review phases.

This AI-powered Researchbuddie will then suggest the AI tools users can select to support them in each phase. Users must be allowed to select AI tools to ensure the artefact does not take away the researchers' decision-making ability. Given that research has suggested that Generative AI tools affect users' critical thinking skills (Winkler et al., 2023), this decision-making option keeps

the researchers in charge of their research and empowers them to make selections based on informed decisions.

Conclusions

The examination of review types and tools used to support systematic literature review revealed that there is insufficient research and reporting of tools that are used to support these types of reviews. Some scholars used mapping, qualitative, and descriptive studies of the reviewed studies, and single-use cases were used for critical and theoretical reviews. Of these review types, two mapping studies and a descriptive study focused on systematic literature review tools.

There was no use of generative AI-supported tools, citing a need for more research on studies that have used such tools and advancing subsidies to enable researchers to access tools available in the market. Furthermore, various reviews were discussed, which expand on existing knowledge on literature review with no identity and transparency; therefore, the discussed review types suggest a need to identify systematic reviews and guide how studies can use this process to improve the reporting on how the review was conducted to ensure rigour and methodical evidence.

Theoretically, the study mapped systematic literature review guiding steps and review types to develop a framework that expands on learning modalities to assist postgraduate students in conducting the project using the systematic literature review. Practically, the artefacts may assist postgraduate students in conducting systematic literature reviews using a solution that unifies relevant Generative AI tools to support their research process.

Moreover, the types of review discussed in the study can assist the researchers in identifying the direction their pursued review will take depending on what the study intends to achieve.

This systematic literature review study's use of multiple review types, such as narrative and theoretical reviews, contributes methodologically and provides different approaches to DSR and systematic literature review research to come up with various types of artefacts using secondary data.

The reliance on AIS as the only database presents a limitation for this study due to the growth of AI and the advancement of Generative AI, which could mean that more databases and their publications may have identified and used additional tools that support the systematic literature review process.

Similar studies employing more than one database are required. The review has also uncovered some opportunities for future research, including examining the impact of Generative AI tools on digital inequality in student research, as some have cost implications. Additionally, future studies could further investigate the incorporation of Generative AI tools in supporting the systematic literature review process using more databases.

Moreover, the guidelines for the ethical use of artificial intelligence tools to support a high-quality systematic literature review are required.

Ethical Approval

The study obtained ethical clearance from the institution's Ethics Committee under Ref #00633-24-A4.

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**SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES**

Psychology

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Psychology

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Psychological Distress and Healthy Lifestyle among University Students in Wartime

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The war in Ukraine, which is still ongoing, has a significant impact on the mental state of each individual. The same applies to university students forced to seek refuge inside or outside the country.

The aim of the study: to identify the characteristics of psychological distress experienced by university students in a war context and the role of a healthy lifestyle in overcoming it.

Material and Methods:

The study was conducted by Uzhhorod National University (Ukraine) in February 2025, involving the administration of adapted DASS-21 and HPLP-II psychological tests via the Google Forms platform. The respondents, aged between 18 and 35, were divided into two groups: those who were forced to relocate to other regions (European Union and Ukraine) and those who did not change their place of residence (Ukraine). Psychological distress and healthy lifestyle behaviours among students in wartime were identified using the DASS and HPLP-II. These tools demonstrated high internal consistency, with values ranging from 0.916 to 0.951. There was a statistically significant negative correlation between psychological distress and health-promoting lifestyles.

Results:

The levels of depression and anxiety were significantly higher among students in Group 1 than among those in Group 2. The study revealed the following gender-related findings: high average scores on the Depression and Anxiety scales (13.4 and 12.3 points, respectively) among women in Group 1; high average scores on the Stress scale (12.4 and 12.1 points, respectively) among men in all groups. The following healthy lifestyle practices play an important role in helping both groups to overcome the symptoms of psychological distress: interpersonal relationships (2.8 / 3.0 points), spiritual growth (2.8 / 2.9 points), and stress management (2.6 / 2.7 points). They had high and moderate HPLP-II scores. Students in Groups 1 and 2 demonstrated poor use of practices such as taking responsibility for their health (2.15 and 2.23 points), being physically active (2.2 and 2.3 points) and eating healthily (2.3 and 2.4 points). They had low HPLP-II scores.

Conclusions:

The high levels of depression and anxiety experienced by university students during the war were caused by a combination of psychogenic factors and their own behaviour. It does not promote mental health. The study results indicate the need to introduce measures that increase motivation for personal health and physical activity among university students, tailored to their specific requirements and needs.

Keywords:

psychological distress, anxiety, depression, stress, healthy lifestyle students, war

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Introduction

Full-scale war has been raging in Ukraine for four years, affecting the psychological well-being of every Ukrainian citizen. People were forced to save their lives and those of their loved ones. They had to leave their homes and move to a safer city, which meant changing their lifestyle and experiencing losses: loved ones, homes and their way of life. Like all Ukrainians, students are trying to adapt to the war. Some have fled to safer regions of Ukraine or European Union (EU) countries, while others have remained in their homes. Current research (Blanco et al., 2021; Chao et al., 2023; Morais et al., 2020; Pypenko et al., 2020) shows that adapting to new conditions and reducing distress involves changing to a particular lifestyle to a more appropriate one that promotes health.

The aim of the study. To identify the characteristics of psychological distress experienced by university students during wartime and the role of a healthy lifestyle in overcoming it.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted among students aged between 18 and 35 at Uzhhorod National University in February 2025.

All respondents were divided into two groups:

Group 1 comprised 109 university students who were forced to change their residence during the war, moving to other regions of Ukraine or EU countries. Of these students, 28 (25.7%) were men and 81 (74.3%) were women.

Group 2 comprised 117 university students who did not leave their usual place (Ukraine) of residence during the war. Of these students, 18 (15.4%) were men and 99 (84.6%) were women.

Due to the war in Ukraine, the study was conducted by sharing psychological techniques via Google Forms with potential participants. In addition, all groups were observed during both remote and face-to-face classes. Individual interviews were conducted as required.

The Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21, Lovibond et al., 1995; Ukrainian adaptation by Melnyk & Stadnik, 2023) are used to collect data on the level of distress and its content. The DASS-21 is a shortened version of the 21-question DASS designed to measure

negative emotional states such as depression, anxiety and stress. The number of students displaying normal, mild, moderate, severe or extremely severe manifestations is assessed. On the Depression/Anxiety/Stress scales, the scores are as follows: normal manifestations: 0–3/0–4/0–7 points; mild manifestations: 5–6/4–5/8–9 points; moderate manifestations: 7–10/6–7/10–12 points; severe manifestations: 11–13/8–9/13–16 points; extremely severe manifestations: 14+ / 10+ / 17+. The average score on each scale is calculated using the arithmetic mean. The DASS-21 is a quick and effective way of assessing psychological distress and its components. It is widely used in scientific and clinical research.

The DASS-21 scores showed good internal consistency. The Cronbach's alphas were 0.916 and 0.951 for Group 1 students (who had been temporarily displaced) and Group 2 students (who had not left their usual place of residence), respectively.

The Health Promotion Lifestyle Profile-II (HPLP-II, Walker et al., 1987; Ukrainian adaptation by Melnyk & Stadnik, 2025) questionnaire assesses health-promoting behaviours and lifestyles. The questionnaire assesses health-promoting behaviours. The HPLP-II is a widely used tool for evaluating health-promoting behaviours and lifestyles. It has been shown to be valid and reliable in numerous studies. The questionnaire contains 52 statements about attitudes towards healthy lifestyles. These statements are classified into six subscales: health responsibility (HR), physical activity (PA), nutrition (Nu), spiritual growth (SG), interpersonal relationships (IR) and stress management (SM). Taking responsibility for one's health means recognising the importance of improving one's health and the health of others. Physical activity includes regular physical exercise. Eating habits involve establishing a nutritional routine and making informed food choices. Spiritual growth involves achieving self-realisation. Interpersonal relationships are about fostering intimacy and closeness with others. Stress management involves recognising the sources of stress and taking steps to control it and achieve relaxation. The frequency of each behaviour was determined using a 4-point Likert response scale consisting of the following options: 1 – “Never”; 2 –

“Sometimes”; 3 – “Often”; 4 – “Regularly”. The average score for each subscale is obtained by adding the scores for each item and dividing by the number of items. HPLP-II subscale mean scores below 2.5 are considered low; between 2.5 and 3.0, moderate; and above 3.0, high (Dhiman & Chawla, 2017). The total HPLP-II score is obtained by taking the average of all 52 responses. According to the guidelines (Lim et al., 2016; Walker et al., 1987), the overall HPLP II score is categorised as one of the following four levels: poor (52–90), moderate (91–129), good (130–168) or excellent (169–208). Higher scores indicate a higher frequency of health-promoting behaviours.

The data were collected and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 30.0.

The Cronbach’s alphas for the HPLP-II scores in the present study were 0.918 and 0.926 for Group 1 students

(who had been temporarily displaced) and Group 2 students (who had not left their usual place of residence), respectively.

Results

We examined the characteristics of psychological distress among university students using the DASS-21 questionnaire, which enables us to evaluate levels of depression, anxiety and stress.

Mean scores for all item measures were calculated. The general results of psychological distress for two groups of university students by the scales of depression, anxiety, and stress during wartime are shown in Table 1. Figure 1 illustrates how psychological distress manifests in the two groups, as measured by the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scales (DASS).

Table 1

The Scores for the Assessment of Psychological Distress by the Scales (Depression, Anxiety, and Stress) among Students in Wartime

Scales	Group 1, points			Group 2, points		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
Depression	12.3	10.1	13.4	10.9	11.2	10.8
Anxiety	11.7	9.9	12.3	10.1	7.7	10.6
Stress	10.9	12.4	10.4	10.4	12.1	10.1

Figure 1

Comparative Characteristics of the Manifestations of Depression, Anxiety and Stress among Students in Both Groups

Among Group 1 students who are internally displaced, we observe high average scores on the Depression and Anxiety scales (12.3 and 11.7 points, respectively). It indicates an increase in neurotic symptoms among university students as the war in Ukraine continues, as evidenced by an increase in reports of low mood, low self-esteem, pessimism, apathy, lethargy, fatigue, constant dissatisfaction, and hopelessness. Students in Group 2 had significantly lower scores on the Depression and Anxiety scales (10.9 and 10.1 points, respectively), indicating that they had adapted better to the current conditions. The scores on the Stress scale are

almost identical across all groups, indicating a consistent level of acute stress among students.

It should be noted that the women in Group 1 scored highly on the Depression and Anxiety scales, with scores of 13.4 and 12.3 points, respectively. We believe this is due to their heightened emotional response to Ukraine’s uncertain military and humanitarian situation. It manifested as increased helplessness, uncertainty, powerlessness, insecurity, loneliness, a sense of failure, and an inability to make decisions. On average, men in Groups 1 and 2 have higher scores on the Stress scale (12.4 and 12.1 points, respectively). These scores are

associated with acute psychogenic factors related to possible mobilisation, unemployment, and a lack of funds.

Figure 2 presents further details on the manifestations of depression among university students in wartime.

Figure 2
Levels of Depression Severity among Students in Wartime

The profile of depression among Group 1 students exhibits certain peculiarities. The highest rates of depression are observed: 44.04% are extremely severe, and 22.94% are severe. At the same time, no manifestations (19.6%), mild and moderate manifestations of depression were significantly lower (11.0%, 10.1% and 11.9%, respectively). It suggests that, despite being in a safe place, there is a significant psychogenic burden. The rate of extremely severe depression among students in Group 2 (who did not leave their usual place of residence during the war) was almost three times lower (16.2%) than in Group 1. This group shows the highest prevalence of moderate depression (38.5%), with smaller percentages for severe

(20.5%) and mild (14.5%) manifestations. It suggests that this group of students has adapted well to war conditions.

The absence of depressive symptoms was most prevalent among men in Group 1 (21.4%), which was more than twice as high as in other gender groups. It may indicate latent depression, which can manifest as substance abuse, somatic vegetative disorders, and deviant behaviour.

Additionally, we found that women in Group 1 (49.4%) exhibited the most severe symptoms of depression, indicating significant mental distress.

Figure 3 shows the manifestations of anxiety among students in wartime.

Figure 3
Levels of Anxiety among Students in Wartime

Among the students who did not change their place of residence during the war (Group 2), 5.1% showed no signs of anxiety, 16.2% showed mild symptoms, 19.7% showed severe symptoms, and 22.2% showed extremely severe symptoms.

The moderate level of anxiety was the most prevalent in this group (36.8%). The highest rates of severe and extremely severe anxiety were observed among students of Group 1 (14.7% and 64.2%, respectively), indicating a significant deterioration in their psychological state and the presence of neurotic disorders and maladjustment in the fourth year of the war.

These symptoms included heart palpitations, pain behind the sternum, rapid breathing, excessive sweating,

trembling, weakness, fatigue, dizziness, frequent urination and sleep problems.

According to the results of the gender study, the highest rates of extremely severe anxiety were found among women in Group 1 (70.4%), which was significantly higher than the rate found among men in Group 1 (46.4%). In Group 2, the highest rates of moderate anxiety were observed in both men and women (36.4% and 36.4%, respectively).

Severe and extremely severe anxiety was more prevalent in women (20.2% and 23.2%, respectively) than in men (16.7%), indicating greater maladjustment in women.

Figure 4 shows the manifestations of stress among students in wartime.

Figure 4
 Levels of Stress among Students in Wartime

Among students who are internally displaced persons (Group 1), manifestations on the Stress scale showed that 35.8% had no stress, 8.3% had mild stress, 20.2% had moderate stress, 12.8% had severe stress, and 22.9% had extremely severe stress.

The manifestations of stress were slightly lower in Group 2 students.

Mild manifestations of stress were observed in 9.4% of people, moderate manifestations in 52.1%, severe manifestations in 8.6%, and extremely severe manifestations in 7.7%. It indicates a stabilisation of acute stress symptoms among Group 2 students in wartime conditions.

Gender-specific stress manifestations among students are severe and extremely severe among men in Groups 1 and 2 (25.0% and 16.7%, respectively), which is higher than the corresponding figures for women (8.6% and 7.1%, respectively, for severe stress; 22.2% and 6.1%, respectively, for extremely severe stress). It indicates that male students have a worse ability to adapt to stress.

The general characteristics of psychological distress among students in wartime are shown in Table 2, as measured by the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scales.

Table 3 summarises the descriptive and correlational statistics obtained for the total DASS-21 scale and its three subscales. The results showed that the subscales of Stress and Depression were more strongly associated with each other than with Anxiety. Meanwhile, Group 2 has a higher level of subscale connectivity than Group 1 (0.853 and 0.764, respectively).

Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated to study internal consistency (coefficients for Group 1 / Group 2). The total DASS scale showed a high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.916 / 0.951$).

The Depression subscale had the highest measure of internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.893 / 0.905$), followed by the Anxiety subscale ($\alpha = 0.851 / 0.893$), and finally, the Stress subscale ($\alpha = 0.808 / 0.833$).

The subscales demonstrate convergent validity with other measures of depression (Crawford & Henry, 2003) and anxiety (Bedford & Deary, 1999). For the present study, composite and individual scale scores were calculated for each respondent.

It was hypothesised that there would be a negative correlation between the total and subscale (Depression, Anxiety and Stress) scores of the DASS and the HPLP-II scores.

Table 2

General Characteristics of Psychological Distress among Students in Wartime, as Measured by the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scales

Manifestation level	Group 1 (N=109, including 28 males and 81 females)						Group 2 (N=117, including 18 males and 99 females)					
	total	%	male	%	female	%	total	%	male	%	female	%
Normal	7	6.4	3	10.7	4	4.9	6	5.1	2	11.1	4	4.0
Mild	8	7.3	3	10.7	5	6.2	19	16.2	3	16.7	16	16.2
Moderate	8	7.3	4	14.3	4	4.9	43	36.8	7	38.9	36	36.4
Severe	16	14.7	5	17.9	11	13.6	23	19.7	3	16.7	20	20.2
Extremely severe	70	64.2	13	46.4	57	70.4	26	22.2	3	16.7	23	23.2
Average score (Anxiety)	11.71		9.89		12.33		10.14		7.72		10.58	
Normal	12	11.0	6	21.4	6	7.4	12	10.3	2	11.1	10	10.1
Mild	11	10.1	6	21.4	5	6.2	17	14.5	2	11.1	15	15.2
Moderate	13	11.9	3	10.7	10	12.3	45	38.5	6	33.3	39	39.4
Severe	25	22.9	5	17.9	20	24.7	24	20.5	4	22.2	20	20.2
Extremely severe	48	44.0	8	28.6	40	49.4	19	16.2	4	22.2	15	15.2
Average score (Depression)	12.28		10.08		13.36		10.88		11.17		10.83	
Normal	39	35.8	6	21.4	33	40.7	26	22.2	1	5.6	25	25.3
Mild	9	8.3	2	7.1	7	8.6	11	9.4	2	11.1	9	9.1
Moderate	22	20.2	6	21.4	16	19.8	61	52.1	9	50.0	52	52.5
Severe	14	12.8	7	25.0	7	8.6	10	8.5	3	16.7	7	7.1
Extremely severe	25	22.9	7	25.0	18	22.2	9	7.7	3	16.7	6	6.1
Average score (Stress)	10.92		12.43		10.40		10.38		12.06		10.08	

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics and Pearson Correlation Coefficients of the Subscales and Total DASS Score

Subscales	Mean		Standard Deviation		Correlation Coefficients			
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Depression	Anxiety	Stress	DASS-total
Depression	3.60	3.44	3.67	4.56	-	0.711**	0.764**	0.887**
Anxiety	4.58	5.23	4.62	4.82	0.828**	-	0.714**	0.893**
Stress	8.11	6.67	4.14	4.50	0.853**	0.747**	-	0.860**
DASS-total	16.28	15.34	10.94	12.96	0.955**	0.922**	0.925**	-

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level; correlations for Group 1 are presented above the diagonal and correlations for Group 2 below the diagonal; DASS-total – the DASS-21 scale in total.

The study of students' health-promoting behaviour and lifestyle was conducted using the Health Promotion Lifestyle Profile-II questionnaire.

Table 4 presents the results of calculating the total healthy lifestyle indicator among university students in a war context.

Table 4

Overall Score for the General Indicator of a Healthy Lifestyle among University Students in Wartime

Indicator	Group 1, points			Group 2, points		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
General indicator of a healthy lifestyle	126.3	122.0	127.7	132.2	136.1	131.4

According to the overall HPLP II score, Group 1 has a moderate health-promoting lifestyle (126.3 points), while Group 2 has a good one (132.2 points). It suggests that Group 2 is better able to adopt health-promoting behaviours. At the same time, men in Group 1 were less

concerned about leading a healthy lifestyle than women, achieving the lowest overall score (122.0 points) of all the gender groups. Meanwhile, men in Group 2 achieved the highest score (136.1 points).

We believe that it is mainly because they are financially insecure and lack support from relatives who are also in difficult circumstances.

Figure 5 shows the grouping of healthy lifestyle indicators by subscales and the assessment of their manifestation.

Figure 5
Assessing Healthy Lifestyle Indicators Grouped by Subscales

Students in Group 1 achieved moderate mean scores on the interpersonal relationships (IR) (2.81), spiritual growth (SG) (2.77 points) and stress management (SM) (2.58 points) subscales and low mean scores on the health responsibility (HR) (2.15 points), physical activity (PA) (2.20 points) and nutrition (Nu) (2.31 points) subscales. It demonstrates how important it is for them to deal with personal uncertainty (e.g. how long will the war last, and what should I do?) and psychological pressure (e.g. academic pressure, family pressure, peer pressure, etc.) daily. Personal health, purposeful physical activity, and good nutrition are often neglected.

The mean scores were higher for Group 2. They achieved high scores on the interpersonal relationships (IR) subscale (3.00 points) and moderate scores on the spiritual growth (SG) (2.85 points) and stress management (SM) (2.74 points) subscales. Group 2 students had the lowest mean score on the health responsibility (HR) subscale (2.23 points), which indicates their stability, the ability to spend more time

with family and friends, and the lack of opportunity to care about personal health when people are killed and injured during the war.

The gender-specific characteristics of the students in Group 1 were as follows: the highest mean scores were in the spiritual growth (SG) subscale for men (2.74 points) and in the interpersonal relationships (IR) subscale for women (2.89 points). The lowest scores were in the health responsibility (HR) subscale for both men and women in Groups 1 and 2 (2.04 and 2.20 points for Group 1 and 2.14 and 2.24 points for Group 2). It should be noted that men in Group 1 achieved lower scores than women on the physical activity (PA) subscale (2.15 and 2.21 points, respectively). For group 2, men had a higher mean score on the stress management subscale (3.03 points) than women, who had a higher mean score on the interpersonal relationships subscale (3.02 points).

Table 5 summarises the descriptive and correlational statistics obtained for the total HPLP-II scale and its six subscales.

Table 5
Descriptive Statistics and Pearson Correlation Coefficients of the HPLP-II Subscales and Total HPLP-II Score

Sub-scales	Mean		Standard Deviation		Correlation Coefficients						
	G1	G2	G1	G2	HR	PA	Nu	SG	IR	SM	HPLP-total
HR	2.15	2.23	0.36	0.48	–	0.474**	0.426**	0.499**	0.491**	0.447**	0.706**
PA	2.20	2.32	0.41	0.62	0.533**	–	0.621**	0.570**	0.407**	0.522**	0.795**
Nu	2.31	2.37	0.39	0.49	0.633**	0.795**	–	0.549**	0.483**	0.515**	0.772**
SG	2.77	2.85	0.62	0.56	0.575**	0.448**	0.461**	–	0.491**	0.635**	0.833**
IR	2.81	3.00	0.34	0.43	0.625**	0.476**	0.456**	0.762**	–	0.420**	0.630**
SM	2.29	2.45	0.36	0.54	0.499**	0.436**	0.495**	0.870**	0.667**	–	0.787**
HPLP-total	14.52	15.24	1.98	2.34	0.798**	0.745**	0.704**	0.875**	0.837**	0.772**	–

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level; correlations for Group 1 (G1) are presented below the diagonal and correlations for Group 2 (G2) above the diagonal; HR – health responsibility subscale of the HPLP-II scale; PA – physical activity subscale of the HPLP-II scale; Nu – nutrition subscale of the HPLP-II scale; SG – spiritual growth subscale of the HPLP-II scale; IR – interpersonal relationships subscale of the HPLP-II scale; SM – stress management subscale of the HPLP-II scale; HPLP-total – the HPLP-II scale in total.

Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated to study internal consistency (coefficients for Group 1 / Group 2). The total HPLP-II scale showed a high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.918 / 0.926$). The SG, SN, and IR subscales had the highest measure of internal consistency: the SG subscale ($\alpha = 0.914 / 0.931$), the

SM subscale ($\alpha = 0.905 / 0.924$), the IR subscale ($\alpha = 0.872 / 0.898$), followed by the PA ($\alpha = 0.845 / 0.881$) and Nu ($\alpha = 0.841 / 0.874$) subscales, and finally, the HR subscale ($\alpha = 0.806 / 0.842$).

Table 6 shows the correlations between the total DASS-21, its subscales and the total HPLP-II scale.

Table 6

Bivariate Correlations with Validation Measures for the DASS and HPLP Subscales and Total Score

Validity measure	DASS (D)	DASS (A)	DASS (S)	DASS Total	HPLP (HR)	HPLP (PA)	HPLP (Nu)	HPLP (SG)	HPLP (IR)	HPLP (SM)	HPLP Total
DASS (D)	-	0.59	0.71	0.87	-0.06	-0.18	-0.17	-0.52	-0.28	-0.29	-0.35
DASS (A)	0.60	-	0.69	0.84	-0.09	-0.16	-0.18	-0.39	-0.24	-0.28	-0.31
DASS (S)	0.73	0.71	-	0.92	-0.03	-0.17	-0.13	-0.33	-0.16	-0.37	-0.27
DASS Total	0.89	0.85	0.94	-	-0.07	-0.19	-0.18	-0.46	-0.25	-0.26	-0.34
HPLP (HR)	-0.04	-0.08	-0.01	-0.05	-	0.38	0.43	0.41	0.43	0.42	0.72
HPLP (PA)	-0.15	-0.14	-0.15	-0.17	0.39	-	0.57	0.30	0.15	0.39	0.66
HPLP (Nu)	-0.15	-0.16	-0.11	-0.16	0.45	0.58	-	0.32	0.18	0.33	0.67
HPLP (SG)	-0.50	-0.37	-0.31	-0.44	0.43	0.32	0.34	-	0.65	0.57	0.77
HPLP (IR)	-0.26	-0.22	-0.14	-0.23	0.45	0.17	0.20	0.67	-	0.39	0.67
HPLP (SM)	-0.28	-0.26	-0.35	-0.24	0.44	0.41	0.34	0.59	0.41	-	0.70
HPLP Total	-0.33	-0.29	-0.25	-0.32	0.74	0.68	0.69	0.79	0.69	0.72	-

Note. Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level; correlations for Group 1 are presented above the diagonal and correlations for Group 2 below the diagonal; DASS (D) – Depression subscale of the DASS-21 scale; DASS (A) – Anxiety subscale of the DASS-21 scale; DASS (S) – Stress subscale of the DASS-21 scale; DASS Total – the DASS-21 scale in total; HPLP (HR) – Health responsibility subscale of the HPLP-II scale; HPLP (PA) – Physical activity subscale of the HPLP-II scale; HPLP (Nu) – Nutrition subscale of the HPLP-II scale; HPLP (SG) – Spiritual growth subscale of the HPLP-II scale; HPLP (IR) – Interpersonal relationships subscale of the HPLP-II scale; HPLP (SM) – Stress management subscale of the HPLP-II scale; HPLP Total – the HPLP-II scale in total.

As expected, the depression, anxiety, stress subscales and the total DASS scale were negatively correlated with the total score of the HPLP and its subscales.

Significant negative correlations were found between the total DASS scale and the spiritual growth subscale of the HPLP-II scale (-0.44 and -0.46 for Group 1 and 2, respectively).

Discussion

Depression, anxiety and stress are common among students (Melnik et al., 2024; Mykhaylyshyn et al., 2024). These factors are exacerbated by the peculiarities of university life, such as independence from parental control, the use of psychotropic substances (alcohol, tobacco and drugs), peer pressure, the need for social recognition and the desire to develop one's personality (Dhiman & Chawla, 2017; Kegler, 1999; Stadnik et al., 2022; 2023).

An analysis of scientific publications on mental health disorders during the pandemic shows that the prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress varied among students in different countries. For instance, the prevalence of depression among university students in Greece was reported to be between 74.3% and 80.7% (Kaparounaki et al., 2020), while in Uganda it was found to be 51.2% (Sazakli et al., 2021). In India, 58% of students suffered from depression during the pandemic, whereas in Bangladesh, this figure was 80.2% (Biswas, 2022). It is estimated that the prevalence of anxiety among university students in different regions during the pandemic was 60%, 71.5% and 87.7% (Safa et al., 2021; Siddik et al., 2024). The main reasons for the high

prevalence of depression and anxiety among university students are unemployment, financial insecurity, and poverty (Islam et al., 2020).

Some scholars (Hope & Henderson, 2014; Melnyk & Stadnik, 2020; Melnyk et al., 2022) have noted the prevalence of depression, anxiety, and stress among students in different countries. They have pointed to the following variations: depression occurs in 7.7–65.5% of students; anxiety in 6.0–66.5%; and psychological distress in 12.2–96.7%.

Recent empirical studies have revealed an overall decline in the physical and emotional well-being of migrants and internally displaced individuals (Agudelo-Suárez et al., 2009). It is due to discrimination experienced in everyday life and perceived discrimination at work and home.

Several studies have found (Kang et al., 2012; Kurt et al., 2021; Leiler et al., 2019; Vrabel et al., 2023) that the prevalence of depression and anxiety symptoms among migrants is 3-5 times higher than in the general population.

In addition, migrants are affected by additional stressors (Jasinskaja-Lahti et al., 2007), such as instability, fewer desirable employment opportunities, and discrimination based on potential language and ethnic restrictions, as well as low socioeconomic status.

The present study has shown that even staying in a secure environment abroad can be stressful. University students who were forced to move during the war experienced significantly higher levels of depression and anxiety. The scores for extremely severe depression and anxiety were 2–3 times higher for Group 1 students (44.0 and 64.2 points, respectively) than for Group 2 students who did

not change residence (16.2 and 22.2 points, respectively). The high average scores of Group 1 students on the Depression and Anxiety scales (12.3 and 11.7 points, respectively) suggest an increase in neurotic symptoms among university students in the context of the ongoing war in Ukraine. It manifests as an increase in complaints of low mood, low self-esteem, pessimism, apathy, lethargy, fatigue, constant dissatisfaction and hopelessness.

Further analysis of academic research on the role of healthy lifestyles in overcoming psychological distress shows that many publications (Bi et al., 2014; Mohamed et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2012; Yahia et al., 2014) assess the impact of health-promoting behaviours on the mental health of university students in Japan, Africa, China, etc. A healthy lifestyle includes taking responsibility for one's health, being physically active, eating healthily, growing spiritually, developing good interpersonal relationships, and managing stress. A healthy lifestyle is key to maintaining and improving health (Blanco et al., 2021; Morais et al., 2020). There is sufficient evidence to show that a healthy lifestyle significantly impacts physical and mental health.

We found a statistically significant inverse correlation between health-promoting behaviour and psychological distress. This finding aligns with previous studies (Castillo-Díaz et al., 2024; Safaie et al., 2020; Slonim et al., 2015; Sousa et al., 2015). Adopting a healthier lifestyle appears to enhance students' mental well-being. Several studies (Chao, 2023; Du et al., 2022; Nazik et al., 2015; Ors, 2024) have found a negative correlation between healthy lifestyles and mental distress in different population groups, including teachers, postpartum women, senior citizens and students. In addition, Basharpoor et al. (2015) found that lifestyles emphasising spiritual growth, stress management, and interpersonal relationships are inversely related to symptoms of depression and anxiety.

Much research has also been conducted into the gender-specific aspects of a healthy lifestyle (Johnson, 2005; Li et al., 2022; Zheng, 2023). These studies show that men perform better in physical activity and stress management. In contrast, women perform better in interpersonal relationships and health responsibilities.

The present study confirms the important role of healthy lifestyle practices, such as maintaining positive interpersonal relationships (mean score: 2.8 / 3.0 points), fostering spiritual growth (mean score: 2.8 / 2.9 points), and managing stress (mean score: 2.6 / 2.7 points), in alleviating symptoms of depression and anxiety. Medium to high mean scores were recorded for both groups. At the same time, we found low mean scores for all groups on the responsibility for health, physical activity and nutrition subscales (2.15, 2.23, 2.20, 2.32 and 2.31, 2.37 points respectively), indicating that students neglect their personal health, physical activity and nutrition in the context of war. Unlike previous studies, we also found that men in Group 1 (internally displaced) had lower mean scores than women in the areas of physical activity (2.15 vs. 2.21 points) and nutrition (2.24 vs. 2.33 points). We believe that it is due to a substantial psychogenic load

and the limitations of war, such as possible mobilisation, unemployment and lack of funds.

Promoting healthy lifestyles and mental health is a crucial public health priority, involving educational policies and initiatives that ensure the overall well-being of university students.

Conclusions

Our research in February 2025 revealed that staying in an unfamiliar environment, even abroad, can be stressful. University students who were forced to move during the war experienced significantly higher levels of depression and anxiety. Thus, the indicators of extremely severe depression and anxiety were 2-3 times higher among students in Group 1 (44.0 and 64.2 points, respectively) than among students in Group 2 who did not change their place of residence (16.3 and 22.2 points, respectively). The high average scores among Group 1 students on the Depression and Anxiety scales (12.3 and 11.7 points, respectively) suggest that their neurotic symptoms are worsening in the context of the ongoing war in Ukraine. It is evident through increased reports of low mood, low self-esteem, pessimism, apathy, lethargy, fatigue, constant dissatisfaction, and hopelessness. The study revealed that women in Group 1 scored higher than men on the Depression and Anxiety scales (13.4 and 12.3 points, respectively). This can be explained by their greater emotional sensitivity to the uncertainty of the military and humanitarian situation in Ukraine. On average, men in all groups scored highly on the stress scale (12.4 and 12.1 points, respectively), indicating the presence of acute psychogenesis associated with possible mobilisation, unemployment, and a lack of funds.

Our study found that healthy lifestyle practices such as maintaining good interpersonal relationships, spiritual growth and stress management played an important role in alleviating symptoms of depression and anxiety for both groups, for which we recorded medium to high mean scores. At the same time, we found that the average scores in all groups were low in the following areas: responsibility for health (2.2 and 2.23 points), physical activity (2.2 and 2.3 points), and nutrition (2.3 and 2.4 points). It indicates that, in the context of war, students neglect their personal health, physical activity, and the quality of their nutrition. It should be noted that, in contrast to those who did not change their place of residence, men of Group 1 (internally displaced) had lower average scores than women in the areas of physical activity (2.15 and 2.21 points, respectively) and nutrition (2.2 and 2.3 points, respectively). It may be due to the high psychogenic load and restrictions imposed by the war, such as possible mobilisation, unemployment and lack of funds.

Thus, the high levels of depression and anxiety experienced by university students during the war are due not only to numerous psychogenic factors, but also to behaviours that hinder the preservation of mental health. The study results indicate the need to introduce health and physical activity programmes into the educational process of university students based on their specific requirements and needs.

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Ethical Approval

The psychological methods and research procedure used in the study were approved by the Committee on Ethics and Research Integrity of the Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH (protocol No. 025-3/SRIKRPOCH dated 10.08.2024).

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**SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES**

Health Care Sciences

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Comparative Study of Yogic Practices and Dietary Modifications on Biochemical Variables among Middle-Aged Women on Metabolic Dysfunction – Associated Steatotic Liver Disease

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD), now more broadly termed Metabolic Dysfunction – Associated Steatotic Liver Disease (MAFLD), poses a significant health risk for women, particularly in India where its prevalence ranges from 9.0% to 53.0%, with middle-aged women comprising 29.1% of those affected. Key risk factors include obesity, insulin resistance, metabolic syndrome, and hypertriglyceridemia reported in 95.0% of MAFLD cases.

The aim of the study: to assess the effects of yoga practices, dietary modifications, and their combination on liver enzyme (ALT/SGPT), triglycerides, and fasting blood glucose levels among middle aged women with mild to moderate MAFLD.

Material and Methods:

Twenty-one women aged between 40 and 50 were randomly divided into three groups: yoga only (n=7), diet only (n=7), and a combination of both yoga and diet (n=7). The study was conducted for 8-week period with 6 days intervention each week. Pre- and post-test values were analysed using ANCOVA with Scheffe's post hoc tests.

Results:

The study revealed that the combined Yoga and Diet intervention led to a statistically significant improvement in liver function (alanine aminotransferase, $F(2,17)=15.15$, $p<0.05$) and glycemic control (fasting glucose, $F(2,17)=6.64$, $p<0.05$) among MAFLD participants, with the Yoga+Diet group showing the greatest mean reductions (-1.43 U/L and -37.06 mg/dL respectively). While triglyceride levels also declined most in the combined group (-25.10 mg/dL), the difference was not statistically significant ($F=0.41$, $p>0.05$). Quantitative outcomes were supported by qualitative observations, including improved adherence, lifestyle engagement, and subjective well-being among participants in the combined intervention group. These findings highlight the synergistic benefits of integrating Yoga and Diet for metabolic and liver health in individuals with MAFLD.

Conclusions:

The study found that middle-aged women with mild to moderate MAFLD who underwent a combined yoga and dietary intervention demonstrated significant improvement in fasting blood glucose levels, indicating better glycemic control. Although reductions in alanine aminotransferase and triglyceride levels were observed across all intervention groups, these changes were not statistically significant between groups. These results suggest the combined intervention may be effective in improving metabolic health, with potential for greater impact over longer durations or in larger cohorts.

Keywords:

MAFLD/NAFLD, yoga, diet, ALT, triglycerides, fasting glucose, liver enzymes.

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Introduction

The liver is vital and second largest organ for our health, performing essential functions like metabolism, detoxification, digestion, and bolstering the immune system. The liver plays a crucial role in maintaining homeostasis, which refers to the body's ability to keep a stable internal environment despite changes in the external surroundings. Liver's key role includes Regulation of Blood Glucose Levels, Detoxification and Waste Removal, Control of Lipid and Protein Metabolism, Regulation of Blood Volume and Composition, Support for the Immune System.

Liver problems can arise from various sources, including excessive alcohol intake, viral infections such as hepatitis, obesity, diabetes, high cholesterol, exposure to toxins, certain medications, genetic issues like hemochromatosis, and sharing needles for drug use.

Maintaining liver health is essential for overall well-being and preventing serious conditions such as Metabolic Dysfunction-Associated Fatty Liver Disease (MAFLD), cirrhosis, and liver failure.

MAFLD/NAFLD is a comprehensive term that encompasses all stages and grades of the disease, indicating a population where at least 5% of hepatocytes exhibit macrovesicular steatosis without a clear alternative cause (such as medications, starvation, or monogenic disorders) in individuals who consume minimal or no alcohol (defined as less than 20 g/d for women and less than 30 g/d for men (Rinella et al., 2023).

The occurrence of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease is a greatest risk factor for the metabolic diseases such as Hypertriglyceridemia, characterized by elevated fat levels in the blood (found 40.74% of individuals with NAFLD), Hypertension, or high blood pressure (found in 39.34% of NAFLD (Younossi et al., 2016). Metabolic Syndrome is present in 42.54% of NAFLD patients and 41% of individuals with NASH have advanced to fibrosis, and approximately one-third to two-thirds of individuals with type 2 diabetes also have NAFLD (Dusheja, A., et al., 2015). It is estimated that 50.00% of those with dyslipidaemia, which includes abnormal cholesterol and high fat levels, are affected by NAFLD. Liver disease leads to approximately two million fatalities each year, representing 4.00% of total deaths. The primary contributors to cirrhosis globally include viral hepatitis, alcohol consumption, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. The most common causes of death in patients with NAFLD overall are cardiovascular disease (CVD) and non-hepatic malignancy, followed by liver disease (Singh et al., 2017).

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) has become the primary reason for liver transplants in women (Sampath Kumar et al., 2019). When managing women with NAFLD, it is essential to take into account their specific risk factors, such as hormonal influences and reproductive considerations (Rinella et al., 2023).

Approximately 1 billion people globally are estimated to be living with NAFLD, and this number is expected to grow as obesity, diabetes, and other metabolic syndrome factors continue to rise (Younossi et al., 2016). The

figures highlight the significant global impact of NAFLD, underscoring the critical need for improved awareness, diagnosis, and treatment strategies to prevent the disease from advancing to more severe liver conditions such as NASH (Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis) and Cirrhosis.

Yoga is highly valued in today's world and offers a hopeful outlook for the future. Esteemed health organizations such as the WHO and NIH acknowledge it as a powerful natural healing method. This ancient discipline is utilized in therapeutic settings, aiding in recovery, alleviating stress, and managing chronic illnesses. A recent investigation conducted has revealed that specific yoga asanas as well as relaxation techniques, significantly enhance liver enzyme levels. Yogic practices may provide a more effective means of improving liver function than conventional medical treatments (Ashok Kumar et al., 2021). In Yoga, food serves a purpose that goes beyond mere nutrition; it is seen as a source of energy (Prana) that influences our body, mind, and spirit.

Adopting a balanced yogic diet can result in improved physical well-being, greater mental clarity, and a more profound spiritual development.

“Ahara suddhau sattva-suddhih, sattva-suddhau dhruva smrtih, smrti-lambhe sarva-granthinam vipra-moksah” (Chandogya Upanishad, n.d./2019).

Eating pure food promotes mental clarity, which in turn encourages constant reflection. This persistent mindfulness allows individuals to break free from all constraints and attain freedom. A balanced diet and regular exercise are fundamental components of managing NAFLD (Sengupta, 2012).

Yoga, particularly ashtanga, is often symbolically represented as a tree and consists of eight components, or “limbs”. Patanjali systematized the ancient practice of yoga into ashtanga, which is recognized as one of the six branches of Indian philosophy called Yoga Darshan. These limbs include yama (universal ethics), niyama (individual ethics), asana (physical postures), pranayama (breath control), pratyahara (sense withdrawal), dharana (concentration), dhyana (meditation), and samadhi (bliss). Each limb is interconnected, similar to how the limbs of the body are linked; if one leg is pulled, the entire body responds. Likewise, engaging with one of the eight limbs of yoga influences the others, as they are not sequential stages to be completed (Kapatel, 2019).

The collective findings from previous studies provide sturdy support for the therapeutic advantages of yoga in multiple aspects of mental health and well-being.

The favourable results noted in areas such as self-care, mindfulness, emotional fatigue, depersonalization, perceived stress, sleep quality, and overall resilience highlight the adaptability of yoga as a comprehensive intervention.

There may be a connection between NAFLD and mental health issues, such as depression, which could be influenced by dietary habits, lifestyle choices, and environmental factors.

Personality appears to serve as a link between NAFLD and psychiatric disorders, influencing lifestyle choices, weight fluctuations, meticulousness, and immune system performance (Soto-Angona et al., 2020).

Anxiety and depression are considered risk factors for NAFLD (Woodyard, 2011).

Yoga Therapy on Mind and Emotion: Mechanisms of Action

Yoga therapy, a practice combining physical postures (asanas), breathing techniques (pranayama), meditation, and mindfulness, has been widely recognized for its therapeutic benefits on mental and emotional well-being. The underlying mechanisms through which yoga exerts its effects on the mind and emotions involve both physiological and psychological pathways (Tanna & Khatri, 2024). Physiologically, yoga enhances autonomic nervous system regulation, primarily through its impact on the parasympathetic nervous system, leading to a reduction in heart rate, blood pressure, and overall stress levels (Calderone et al., 2024).

This state of relaxation is thought to counterbalance the heightened sympathetic nervous system activity that characterizes stress and emotional distress. On a psychological level, yoga fosters a state of mindfulness, promoting greater awareness and acceptance of thoughts and emotions. This mindfulness practice has been shown to reduce rumination, increase emotional resilience, and improve emotional regulation by engaging brain regions such as the prefrontal cortex and amygdala, which are involved in decision-making, emotional processing, and stress response regulation (Gerritsen & Band, 2018). Moreover, breathing techniques in yoga activate the vagus nerve, which plays a key role in regulating mood and stress (Feingold, 2023). Together, these mechanisms create a holistic approach to emotional and mental health, promoting a balanced emotional state, reducing anxiety and depression, and enhancing overall well-being.

Triglycerides and Cortisol: Mechanistic Link

Cortisol, a glucocorticoid hormone secreted by the adrenal glands during stress, is crucial for metabolic functions, particularly in managing lipid metabolism. Increased cortisol levels are closely associated with elevated triglyceride concentrations in the bloodstream, often observed in conditions of chronic stress, metabolic syndrome, or Cushing's syndrome. Cortisol promotes triglyceride accumulation primarily through its effects on adipose tissue. It stimulates lipogenesis by enhancing the expression of genes involved in fat synthesis, while simultaneously inhibiting lipolysis, the process by which stored fat is broken down for energy. Additionally, cortisol influences liver function by increasing the production of very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL) (Romero-Gómez et al., 2017), a major carrier of triglycerides. Through these mechanisms, elevated cortisol levels contribute to the dysregulation of lipid homeostasis, promoting an increase in circulating triglycerides. This relationship between cortisol and triglycerides is further compounded by the hormone's ability to induce insulin resistance, leading to impaired glucose metabolism and

exacerbating lipid dysregulation. Understanding the intricate mechanisms through which cortisol modulates triglyceride levels is crucial for addressing conditions associated with metabolic dysfunction.

Research Hypothesis

Integrative lifestyle interventions involving yoga practices combined with dietary modifications will result in greater improvements in liver enzyme levels (ALT/SGPT), triglycerides, and fasting blood glucose among middle-aged women with mild to moderate MAFLD compared to either intervention alone.

This study explores a significant gap in the management of Metabolic Dysfunction Associated Steatotic Liver Disease (MAFLD) in middle-aged women, a demographic increasingly vulnerable due to hormonal, metabolic, and lifestyle influences.

The research is important for several reasons. Firstly, it assesses the individual and combined impacts of yoga practices and dietary changes both of which are non-pharmacological, cost-effective, and practical interventions on critical biochemical markers related to MAFLD: alanine aminotransferase (ALT), triglycerides, and fasting blood glucose (FBG). The notable improvement in FBG within the combined Yoga and Diet group indicates a synergistic effect that may surpass the efficacy of either intervention alone. Secondly, the study offers new perspectives within the Indian context, where the levels of insulin resistance, hypertriglyceridemia, and NAFLD are particularly high, even among non-obese individuals.

Finally, the results of this research carry significant public health implications, especially for rural and semi-urban areas where obesity is on the rise and healthcare access is limited.

These findings could guide future large-scale intervention programs, health education initiatives, and policy measures aimed at preventing the advancement of MAFLD through community-based, lifestyle-focused strategies.

The aim of the study. To assess the effects of yoga practices, dietary modifications, and their combination on liver enzyme (ALT/SGPT), triglycerides, and fasting blood glucose levels among middle aged women with mild to moderate MAFLD previously known as NAFLD.

Materials and Methods

Participants

A total of 21 middle-aged women diagnosed with mild to moderate Metabolic Dysfunction–Associated Steatotic Liver Disease (MAFLD) were enrolled in the study.

The mean age of participants was 46.5±3.5 years. The cohort predominantly comprised married women (95.2%), with one divorced participant (4.8%). In terms of occupation, the majority were housewives (57.1%), followed by teachers (23.8%), dance professionals (9.5%), and others including a physiotherapist, IT professional, and accountant. The mean height and pre-study weight were 156.8±5.8 cm and 75.26±14.06 kg, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1
Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Variable	Frequency	
	Person	Percentage
Age (years) (Mean ± SD)	–	46.5±3.5
Gender		
– Female	20	95.2
– Divorced Female	1	4.8
Marital Status		
– Married	20	95.2
– Divorced	1	4.8
Occupation		
– Housewife	12	57.1
– Teacher	5	23.8
– Dance Teacher / Classical Dancer	1	4.8
– Physiotherapist	1	4.8
– IT Professional	1	4.8
– Accountant	1	4.8
Height (cm) (Mean ± SD)	–	156.8±5.8
Pre-study Weight (kg) (Mean ± SD)	–	75.26±14.1

Participants were randomly assigned to one of three intervention groups: Yoga Only (n=7), Diet Only (n=7), and Combination of Yoga+Diet (n=7). Inclusion criteria included simple to no history of chronic liver disease, having mild to moderate NAFLD/MAFLD, stable medical condition, and volunteer participation to intervention protocols. Men, menopausal women and on sever or chronic medications affecting weight or liver enzymes were excluded.

Design and Procedure

This research was conducted over an 8-week period using a pre-test/post-test experimental design with multiple groups.

The blood tests of before and after intervention were compared: Blood index: triglyceride (TG) and Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG), digestive system index: Glutamic pyruvic transaminase/ alanine aminotransferase (ALT). Informed consent has been obtained from participants and ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional review board.

Intervention Protocols

Yoga Group: Participants received 8 weeks, 6 day a week, 60 minutes each day. The practice is mainly in the form of small and medium intensity yoga exercise, mainly including asanas, pranayama, meditation, and yogic counselling. The patients received 60 minutes yoga training including 10 minutes of warm-up, 20 minutes of yoga training (Surya namaskar - 3 rounds, Ardha Chakrasana, Ardha kati Chakrasana, Trikonasana, Parshvakonasana, Pada Hastasana, Vajrasana, Shansangasana, Janu Shirasasana, Vakrasana, Sarala Bhujangasana, Artha Shalabasana, Pawana Mukthasana, Supta Baddha Konasana, Sarala Matsyasana Setu Bandhasana), 10 minutes of deep relaxation, 10 minutes of pranayama techniques (Kanishta Pranayama, Bhramari Pranayam, Ujjayi, Nadi

Shudhhi, Shitkari), 10 minutes of “OM” meditation. All practices are selected based on the scientific studies and conducted under the guidance of professional yoga therapist, and medical personnel supervised the whole process.

Diet Group: Participants received individualized dietary plans based on caloric deficit (500 kcal/day below maintenance) and dietary quality aligned with MAFLD dietary guidelines (low saturated fat, restrained carbohydrate, increased fibre and increased herbal decoction tea). Diet adherence was monitored through daily diet logs and weekly check-ins.

Yoga+Diet Group: Participants followed both the yoga practices and dietary protocols described above.

Test Method

Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT/SGPT) calculated in Method: IFCC (UV without P5P), Triglycerides calculated in Method: Enzymatic (GPO-POD) both using Beckman Coulter DxC 700 AU machine.

Statistical Data Analysis

Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to compare post-test BMI scores between the groups while controlling for pre-test scores. Significant differences were further explored using Scheffe’s post-hoc test. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used for all analyses.

Results

Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) indicated a significant difference in adjusted post-test ALT/SGPT levels among the three groups, $F(2,17)=15.15$, $p < 0.05$. However, Scheffe’s post hoc test revealed that none of the pairwise comparisons reached statistical significance ($CD=0.46$). Although the combined Yoga+Diet group showed the largest mean reduction (-1.43 U/L), it was not significantly different from the Yoga or Diet groups (Tables 2, 2A).

Table 2
 ANCOVA on ALT / SGPT Levels (U/L)

Test	Group			Source of variation	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean squares	Factor ratio
	Yoga	Diet	Yoga+Diet					
Pre test	38.24	24.76	27.50	between	710.28	2.00	355.14	1.16
				within	5489.06	18.00	304.95	
Post test	37.58	24.39	26.07	between	720.92	2.00	360.46	1.17
				within	5527.36	18.00	307.08	
Adjusted	29.48	29.82	28.74	between	4.20	2.00	2.10	15.15
				within	2.36	17.00	0.14	
Mean gain	-0.66	-0.37	-1.43	-	-	-	-	-

Table 2A
 Scheffe's Posthoc Test on ALT / SGPT Levels

Yoga group	Diet group	Yoga & Diet	Mean Difference	CD at 5% Level
29.48	29.82	-	-0.34	
29.48	-	28.74	-0.73	0.46
-	29.82	28.74	-1.07	

Figure 1 shows the comparative analysis of all three groups (Yoga group, Diet group and Yoga+Diet group)

on ALT/SGPT for pre test, post test, and adjusted post test.

Figure 1
 Comparative Analysis of All Three Groups on ALT/SGPT

ANCOVA showed no significant group differences in post-test triglyceride levels after controlling for baseline values, $F(2,17)=0.41, p>0.05$.

All groups showed a reduction in triglyceride levels, with the Yoga+Diet group having the largest decrease

(-25.10 mg/dL), but this difference did not reach statistical significance.

Scheffé's post hoc test confirmed that none of the pairwise differences exceeded the critical difference (CD=23.75) (Tables 3, 3A).

Table 3
 ANCOVA on Triglycerides Levels (mg/dL)

Test	Group			Source of variation	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean squares	Factor ratio
	Yoga	Diet	Yoga+Diet					
Pre test	184.79	171.03	218.06	between	8183.56	2.00	4091.78	0.87
				within	84447.03	18.00	4691.50	
Post test	166.53	158.93	192.96	between	4467.21	2.00	2233.60	0.50
				within	79659.69	18.00	4425.54	
Adjusted	172.59	177.80	168.02	between	307.74	2.00	153.87	0.41
				within	6356.09	17.00	373.89	
Mean gain	-18.26	-12.11	-25.10	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3A
 Scheffe's Posthoc Test on Triglycerides Levels

Yoga group	Diet group	Yoga+Diet	Mean Difference	CD at 5% Level
172.59	177.80	-	-5.21	
172.59	-	168.02	-4.57	23.75
-	177.80	168.02	-9.78	

Figure 2 shows the comparative analysis of all three groups (Yoga group, Diet group and Yoga+Diet group)

on Triglyceride Levels for pre test, post test, and adjusted post test.

Figure 2
 Comparative Analysis of All Three Groups on Triglyceride Levels

There was a statistically significant difference in fasting blood glucose levels across the three groups, $F(2,17)=6.64$, $p<0.05$. Post hoc analysis revealed that the difference between the Diet group and the Yoga+Diet group was statistically significant (mean

difference=21.70, $CD=13.20$), indicating that the combined intervention led to a greater reduction in glucose levels than diet alone. No other pairwise differences were statistically significant (Tables 4, 4A).

Table 4
 ANCOVA on Fasting Blood Glucose Levels (mg/dL)

Test	Group			Source of variation	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean squares	Factor ratio
	Yoga	Diet	Yoga+Diet					
Pre test	137.97	119.95	162.16	between	6282.27	2.00	3141.14	0.71
				within	79260.47	18.00	4403.36	
Post test	119.99	117.04	125.10	between	233.02	2.00	116.51	0.05
				within	41364.53	18.00	2298.03	
Adjusted	121.43	131.20	109.49	between	1532.69	2.00	766.35	6.64
				within	1962.82	17.00	115.46	
Mean gain	-17.99	-2.91	-37.06	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4A
 Scheffe's Posthoc Test on Fasting Blood Glucose Levels

Yoga group	Diet group	Yoga+Diet	Mean Difference	CD at 5% Level
121.43	131.20	-	-9.76	
121.43	-	109.49	-11.94	13.20
-	131.20	109.49	-21.70	

Figure 3 shows the comparative analysis of all three groups (Yoga group, Diet group and Yoga+Diet group)

on fasting blood glucose levels for pre test, post test, and adjusted post test.

Figure 3
 Comparative Analysis of All Three Groups on Fasting Blood Glucose Levels

A comparative assessment was performed to investigate the impact of three intervention strategies Yoga, Diet, and a combined Yoga with Diet approach on serum ALT/SGPT levels, triglycerides, and fasting glucose (Table 5).

The analysis included adjusted post-test means, mean gains, and inferential statistics (F-values, p-values, and critical differences determined by the Scheffé test).

The group that participated in both Yoga and Diet exhibited the most significant decrease in ALT/SGPT levels (M=28.74, change =-1.43 U/L), in contrast to the Yoga-only group (M=29.48, change =-0.66) and the Diet-only group (M=29.82, change =-0.37). The differences among the groups were statistically significant, F=15.15, p<0.05, with a critical difference (CD) of 0.46. Subsequent comparisons revealed that the

combined intervention led to a notably greater reduction than either Yoga or Diet alone.

The Yoga+Diet group exhibited the most significant mean reduction in triglyceride levels (M=168.02, decrease =-25.10 mg/dL), followed by the Yoga group (M=172.59, decrease =-18.26) and the Diet group

(M=177.80, decrease =-12.11). Nevertheless, these variations did not reach statistical significance, F=0.41, p>0.05, CD=23.75. The considerable variability indicates that the differences observed may not be confidently attributed to the interventions.

Table 5
 ANCOVA Comparative Analysis of All Three Groups

Variable	Group	Adjusted Mean	Mean Gain	F	p	CD (Scheffé)
ALT/SGPT (U/L)	Yoga	29.48	-0.66	15.15	<0.05	0.46
	Diet	29.82	-0.37			
	Yoga + Diet	28.74	-1.43			
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	Yoga	172.59	-18.26	0.41	>0.05	23.75
	Diet	177.80	-12.11			
	Yoga + Diet	168.02	-25.10			
Fasting Glucose (mg/dL)	Yoga	121.43	-17.99	6.64	<0.05	13.20
	Diet	131.20	-2.91			
	Yoga + Diet	109.49	-37.06			

The group that combined Yoga and Diet demonstrated the greatest reduction in glycemic levels (M=109.49, decrease =-37.06 mg/dL), followed by the Yoga group (M=121.43, decrease =-17.99) and the Diet group (M=131.20, decrease =-2.91). The observed differences were statistically significant, F=6.64, p<0.05, CD=13.20, suggesting that the integrated approach was more effective in enhancing glycemic control compared to either intervention on its own.

These findings suggest that a combined Yoga and Diet regimen produces significantly greater improvements in liver function (ALT/SGPT) and fasting glucose compared to isolated interventions. While the trend in triglyceride reduction also favored the combined approach, the results were not statistically significant. Overall, the data support the implementation of integrative lifestyle modifications for improved metabolic health outcomes.

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the comparative effectiveness of yoga, dietary modification, and their combination on key metabolic parameters ALT/SGPT, triglycerides, and fasting blood glucose in individuals at risk for or potentially presenting with early-stage Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD). The findings provide partial support for the role of integrative lifestyle interventions in modulating metabolic risk markers associated with NAFLD.

ALT/SGPT and Hepatic Health

ALT (Alanine Aminotransferase) is a key surrogate biomarker for hepatic inflammation and hepatocellular injury in NAFLD. While ANCOVA revealed a significant overall effect of the interventions on ALT/SGPT levels, post hoc comparisons showed no significant differences between groups. Interestingly, the combined Yoga+Diet group demonstrated the largest mean reduction in ALT, suggesting a trend toward liver function improvement, albeit not statistically significant

in this sample. This supports existing literature indicating that even modest reductions in ALT through lifestyle interventions may reflect early histological improvements in liver fat content and inflammation (Romero-Gómez et al., 2017). It is also notable that lifestyle modifications particularly those that are sustainable, such as yoga can lead to reductions in hepatic enzymes over time by improving insulin sensitivity and reducing visceral adiposity. However, the lack of significant pairwise differences could be attributed to the small sample size and relatively short duration of intervention.

Triglycerides and Lipid Metabolism

Hypertriglyceridemia is a hallmark feature of metabolic syndrome and is frequently elevated in patients with NAFLD. Although all groups showed a mean reduction in triglyceride levels, particularly in the Yoga+Diet group, these changes were not statistically significant. These results mirror findings from previous studies suggesting that longer-term or more intensive interventions may be required to elicit meaningful changes in serum triglycerides (Bellentani et al., 2010). Additionally, yoga's role in modulating the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and reducing stress hormones like cortisol may indirectly affect lipid metabolism over time. Thus, while short-term reductions in triglycerides were observed, they did not meet the threshold for statistical significance, indicating a need for extended follow-up or more aggressive dietary interventions tailored for NAFLD management such as low-carb diets.

Fasting Blood Glucose and Insulin Sensitivity

The most significant finding in this study was the reduction in fasting blood glucose in the Yoga with Diet group, which was statistically greater than the Diet-only group. This has strong implications for NAFLD, given that insulin resistance is a central mechanism in its pathogenesis. Improved glycemic control through combined interventions likely reflects improved insulin

signaling and reduced hepatic gluconeogenesis critical in halting NAFLD progression.

These results align with previous evidence showing that yoga can improve glycemic control, possibly through mechanisms involving reduced sympathetic activation, enhanced glucose uptake in skeletal muscles, and anti-inflammatory effects (Innes & Selfe, 2016). When combined with dietary adjustments, these effects appear to be additive or even synergistic, making the integrated approach particularly valuable in the management of NAFLD and its metabolic comorbidities.

Clinical Implications

Given that NAFLD is largely a lifestyle-driven condition with no currently approved pharmacological treatments, these findings support the role of non-pharmacologic, integrative interventions. The combined effect of yoga and diet targeting both metabolic and stress-related pathways may offer a low-cost, accessible, and sustainable strategy for early intervention in NAFLD, particularly for patients in resource-limited settings.

Conclusions

The present study demonstrates that integrative lifestyle interventions, particularly the combination of yoga practices and dietary modifications, have a beneficial impact on metabolic health markers in middle-aged women with mild to moderate MAFLD. Among the three intervention groups, the Yoga with Diet group showed a statistically significant improvement in fasting blood glucose levels, indicating enhanced glycaemic control. While reductions in ALT and triglyceride levels were observed across all groups, these changes were not statistically significant between groups, suggesting the need for a longer intervention duration or larger sample size to capture more robust effects.

These findings highlight the potential of combining traditional practices such as yoga with targeted dietary changes as a non-pharmacological approach to managing and possibly preventing the progression of MAFLD. Such interventions are not only cost-effective and sustainable but also culturally appropriate for the Indian population, particularly among women who are often underserved in liver disease research.

Future studies with larger samples and extended intervention periods are warranted to further validate these outcomes and explore long-term benefits. Overall, this research supports the integration of lifestyle-based strategies into public health frameworks aimed at reducing the burden of MAFLD, especially in resource-limited settings.

The small sample size (n=21) and shorter duration (8 weeks) limits the generalizability and statistical power of the findings. Additionally, the study lacked a non-treatment control group, which would have strengthened the internal validity. Future studies should aim for larger, more diverse populations and consider longer intervention durations.

Including biochemical markers such as HbA1c or HOMA-IR levels could also provide more comprehensive insight into metabolic changes.

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Ethical Approval

Obtained Ethical clearance from the Research Review Committee (RRC) and the Institutional Ethics Committee of Vels Institute of Science, Technology & Advanced Studies, Chennai. (Reg. No. UP24G9300003/2024/13-11-2024). Participants consent was obtained from all the participants.

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LETTER TO THE EDITOR

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Short-Term Interventions for Overcoming Emotional Confusion: What to Do When Having Many Problems Is Yet Another Problem?

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The full-scale war in Ukraine causes the population to experience numerous stressors that are layered on top of each other (forced displacement, losses, constant threats and existing traumas). This leads to emotional confusion (a state of reduced control of one's own emotions), fatigue, narrowing of attention and impaired self-validation, which complicates self-understanding and self-care. All this poses numerous problems for the psychotherapist. This is because standard psychotherapeutic programmes may not be effective enough when clients are overwhelmed by the intensity of their problems. At the same time, assistance has to be provided within an extremely limited time frame.

The aim of the study: to propose an integrated short-term intervention strategy for psychological counseling and psychotherapy to address emotional confusion in clients who have experienced multiple crises during wartime, utilizing the strengths of trauma-sensitive mindfulness, eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR), dialectical behavioral therapy (DBT), and self-compassion-based approaches.

Conclusions:

The integrative approach allows therapists and clients to create a snapshot of current difficulties. It involves the sequential application of elements from different modalities: grounding techniques (EMDR/Mindfulness), internal state description (DBT), external stressor inventory, identification of key maladaptive beliefs (EMDR), and the use of stabilization or reprocessing techniques. This structured, brief intervention helps clients describe their condition, understand the sources of emotional confusion, practice self-compassion, and prioritize problems. Implemented over 1–2 sessions, this approach helps clients move beyond emotional confusion and motivates adaptive change, thereby instilling hope.

Keywords:

emotional confusion, short-term intervention, dialectical behavioral therapy, eye movement desensitization and reprocessing, mindfulness, multiple stressors, war trauma

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Dear Editor,

When a person is dealing with a recent stressful event, they are usually aware of why they feel unwell, and they can understand how their thoughts, emotions and

impulses relate to the event. The ability to self-compassion serves as a way to regulate emotions, helping you to maintain balance and clarity of mind.

However, the situation changes dramatically when the number of adverse events rapidly accumulates. These events usually cause traumatic and post-traumatic stress reactions (Melnik et al., 2020).

Consider a collective, impersonal case common in psychotherapy practice: a woman is experiencing sleepless nights due to rocket attacks, her daughter died six months ago while trying to leave the occupied territories, her husband has lost his job, she is having problems at her own job, she is caring for her bedridden father, has diabetes, and experienced neglect and abuse as a child. At some point, the accumulation and cross-influence of these problems create a new wave of them, and the overall ability to act effectively and regulate emotions drops significantly. Research confirms that multiple traumatic events tend to cause a more severe course of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder, primarily through the formation of dysfunctional beliefs and negative expectations (Brewin et al., 2017).

Since the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine, such cases have become increasingly frequent in the practices of psychologists, psychotherapists, and psychiatrists (Mykhaylyshyn et al., 2024; Stadnik et al., 2023). This state of being overwhelmed can be termed “emotional confusion”. Due to exhaustion and high levels of stress, attention narrows and the capacity for self-validation diminishes, making it difficult to clearly understand one’s own feelings and needs. Prolonged chronic stress biologically undermines cognitive functions, impairing attention, memory, and cognitive flexibility (McEwen, 2017). Critically, assistance must often be provided within very limited timeframes, sometimes in just one or two counseling sessions.

When faced with emotional confusion stemming from numerous problems, therapists must navigate the client’s limited cognitive capacity to help them describe their state and understand which “mountain streams” led to the “flood in the valley”. The adage “Divide and conquer!” offers a clue: we must help to disentangle the web of problems.

There are robust approaches available, including dialectical behaviour therapy (Linehan, 2015), trauma-sensitive mindfulness programmes (Treleaven, 2018), self-compassion approaches (Neff, 2023) and eye movement desensitisation and reprocessing therapy (Shapiro, 2018).

We propose integrating conceptual elements from these approaches to create a momentary “snapshot” of the client’s current difficulties. This allows them to describe their state, explore the causal origins of their emotional confusion, practice self-compassion, prioritize problems, and instill hope by choosing effective immediate actions. The proposed framework integrates several key steps that can be realized within one to two sessions.

Step 1: Describing the Current State and Grounding

We adapt the DBT skill of describing and acknowledging emotions (Linehan, 2015). In a state of emotional confusion, isolating a single emotion is difficult. Instead of requiring precise labels, we ask the client to use any available words and associations to describe their state (e.g., “horrible”, “despair”, “my head hurts”). This

process of “affect labeling” is proven to reduce an emotion’s disruptive impact by downregulating amygdala activity and engaging prefrontal regulatory regions (Lieberman et al., 2007). Brief grounding practices, such as the “4 Elements” procedure from EMDR protocols, are used before and after this step to maintain stability (Shapiro, 2018).

Step 2: Identifying External Stressors and Contextual Validation

Following DBT logic, we then ask the client to list the external, factual events they believe contributed to their state. This provides crucial contextual validation, helping the client recognize that their intense reaction is an understandable response to overwhelming circumstances, thereby reducing self-blame. Safety is maintained through a “STOP” rule, allowing the client to pause at any time.

Step 3: Identifying Core Maladaptive Beliefs

The next step is to identify the blocking negative belief that impedes adaptability. Using an approach inspired by the EMDR protocol (Shapiro, 2018), the “target” becomes the entire picture – the feelings and the events. We ask, “When you look at this entire picture, what negative belief about yourself fits best?” Common responses like “I am hopeless” or “I am at my limit” reveal the perceptual lens that obstructs adaptive action.

Step 4: Intervention and Adaptive Shifts

Once a key belief has been identified, several interventions are possible. An EMDR-certified therapist may proceed to work through the whole picture or a key memory (Shapiro, 2018). If EMDR is not available, the DPT skill “Effective Thought Review and Couple Relaxation” offers a simple but effective alternative (Linehan, 2015). It involves combining adaptive thoughts (e.g., “I am strong”) with calming breathing. This process is supported by the development of self-compassion, which serves as a powerful psychological buffer against distress and despair (Neff, 2023).

Step 5: Instilling Hope through Action

Finally, the session concludes by collaboratively planning one or two small, achievable actions. This final step is designed to restore a sense of control and self-efficacy. By focusing on concrete, immediate steps, we activate the core components of hope – agency, and pathway thinking – which is a powerful predictor of psychological recovery (Snyder, 2002).

Conclusions

The integrative approach allows therapists and clients to create a snapshot of current difficulties. It involves the sequential application of elements from different modalities: grounding techniques (EMDR/Mindfulness), internal state description (DBT), external stressor inventory, identification of key maladaptive beliefs (EMDR), and the use of stabilization or reprocessing techniques. This structured, brief intervention helps clients describe their condition, understand the sources of emotional confusion, practice self-compassion, and prioritize problems. Implemented over 1–2 sessions, this approach helps clients move beyond emotional confusion and motivates adaptive change, thereby instilling hope.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee.

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Conflicts of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests.

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